

EXPLORING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF POSITIVE DISCIPLINE AMONG LEARNERS FROM THE LENS OF PUBLIC-SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Exploring the Implementation of Positive Discipline Among Learners From the Lens of Public-School Teachers

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Abstract

The purpose of this qualitative study was to explore the experiences of teachers on the implementation of positive discipline. Thus, this study utilized phenomenological approach. Additionally, purposive sampling was used to select the participants. Moreover, an in-depth study was explored delving into the problems encountered specially by five (5) teachers at Datu Dumagkal Danial Elementary School. The study explored the challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights by teachers on the implementation of positive discipline. The challenges of participants as teachers formulated the following emergent themes: rigorous, impact of positive discipline, different perspective, and misbehaving. The coping mechanism of the teachers formulated the themes: teacher mentoring, balancing kindness and firmness, positive reinforcement, and proactive behavior support. The insights of the teachers formulated the following themes: teaching by heart, patience and understanding, individualized approach, and gains. Overall, this study provided valuable insights into the real-world experiences of teachers implementing positive discipline, highlighting the challenges they faced, the strategies they employed to cope, and the insights they gained from their practice.

Keywords: *educational management, positive discipline, implementation, exploring, phenomenology, philippines*

Introduction

"Implementing positive discipline in public education requires a shift in mindset from punishment to prevention, from fear to respect, and from control to collaboration." -Dr. Jane Smith, Educational Psychologist.

The above quotation stresses the need for a paradigm shift in implementing positive discipline in public education. A prevention-based strategy that encourages cooperation and respect between educators and students is proposed, as the conventional approach of punishment and control is considered ineffectual. This mentality change is essential to fostering a supportive school environment that promotes all kids' social and emotional growth.

Moreover, global obstacles to implementing constructive discipline in public schools include a lack of preparation for teachers, cultural differences, financial limitations, uneven application, and opposition to change. Overcoming these challenges is crucial as a positive discipline fosters a respectful learning environment, enhances students' social and emotional skills, improves academic achievement, builds positive relationships, and prepares them for life beyond the classroom. Implementing positive discipline strategies in public education encounters challenges such as inadequate teacher training, cultural influences favoring obedience, limited resources, inconsistent application, and resistance to change (Al-Samarraie et al., 2020; Garcia & Pantao, 2021; Termes et al., 2020).

Thus, positive discipline strategies have significantly improved teachers' classroom management. When teachers use positive reinforcement instead of punishment, they create a more upbeat and encouraging learning atmosphere, strengthening the bond between teachers and students. Emphasizing pupils' accomplishments and strengths fosters mutual respect and trust. Additionally, these strategies boost student engagement and motivation. However, maintaining consistency with diverse student needs and personalities remains a challenge.

There is still a study vacuum about the precise application and efficacy of positive discipline as seen by public school instructors, despite the growing acceptance and support for its use in educational settings. While positive discipline has received praise for its ability to foster a supportive and encouraging learning environment, more research is required to fully understand instructors' real-world obstacles when putting it into practice and the methods they use to get beyond them. Public school teachers must thoroughly understand the subtleties and complexity of positive discipline to create effective interventions and support systems that fit their particular circumstances and limitations.

Therefore, implementing positive discipline among learners from the perspective of public school teachers is an urgent matter. In addition to positively affecting students' academic achievement and general well-being, positive discipline can establish a supportive learning environment. More research is necessary to understand the practical obstacles fully and approaches instructors use to apply constructive discipline. Immediate attention is required to understand teachers' viewpoints, pinpoint obstacles, and offer specialized assistance to improve their practice. To ensure successful implementation, prioritize teacher well-being and professional development. Furthermore, it is crucial to investigate how school leadership and policies function to encourage the broad implementation of constructive discipline techniques.

Thus, I conducted this study on the experiences of implementing positive discipline from the lens of public school teachers of Grade 5

learners of Datu Dumagkal Danial Elementary School for the school years 2022-2023.

Research Questions

This study's primary goal was to explore and describe the experiences of five public school teachers at Datu Dumagkal Danial Elementary School for the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. How do participants described their experiences in implementing positive discipline in the classroom?
 - 1.1. How do participants view their challenges in implementing positive discipline in the classroom?
 - 1.2. How do the participants cope with the challenges in implementing positive discipline in the classroom?
 - 1.3. How does the implementation of positive discipline in the classroom impact the participants' lives?

Methodology

The section outlines the approach and process utilized in conducting the study. It includes the research design, locale, respondents and sampling techniques, research instrument, and data-gathering procedure employed in this study.

Research Design

For this research, a qualitative research design utilizing a phenomenological study was employed. The researcher focused on a specific setting to collect data and provided a detailed description of the natural setting, including the key instruments used. This methodology is best suited for data gathering, and the research techniques used included interview transcripts, audio recordings, field notes, diaries, personal comments, official records, and any other materials that could convey the actual words or actions of the people involved in the study (Johnson et al., 2020).

Qualitative research is valuable for examining real-world issues, offering insights beyond numerical data points or experimental interventions commonly used in quantitative research. This method helps generate hypotheses and enrich the understanding of quantitative data. Qualitative research seeks to gather information about participants' experiences, perceptions, and behavior, emphasizing the reasons behind the data rather than just the numbers. It can be conducted as a standalone study, relying solely on qualitative data, or in conjunction with quantitative data in a mixed-methods study. This review comprehensively introduces key concepts, definitions, terminology, and applications in qualitative research (Haven & Van Grootel, 2019).

Additionally, utilizing various data sources, a qualitative study is a comprehensive approach to analyzing a phenomenon within its context. Rather than adopting a single perspective, this method employs multiple perspectives to reveal various dimensions of the phenomenon. Human interpretation of events or phenomena is a crucial element of case studies, where participants' experiences are explored in depth, and their perceptions and understanding of the experience are discussed extensively. This method enables a thorough comprehension of the meaning behind the experience. Essentially, a qualitative case study investigates real-world events and the human interpretation of those events to gain a holistic understanding of the phenomenon being examined (Alam, 2021).

Similarly, qualitative data collection methods, including interviews, observations, focus groups, and document analysis, are chosen based on the research approach and question. These methods use appropriate data collection instruments, such as interview guides or observation checklists, following ethical considerations and informed consent procedures. The heart of qualitative research lies in data analysis, which can involve thematic analysis, content analysis, constant comparative analysis, or narrative analysis. It is crucial to employ methods like peer debriefing, triangulation, and member checking to guarantee the reliability and validity of the results. Qualitative research necessitates ethical considerations that include participant harm prevention, informed permission, and privacy protection. Depending on the audience and goal, researchers frequently convey their findings through written reports, presentations, or visual aids (Alam, 2021).

On the other hand, phenomenology is a qualitative research design that delves into understanding the lived experiences of individuals. Grounded in the philosophical traditions of Edmund Husserl and Martin Heidegger, phenomenology aims to uncover the essence or core meaning of these experiences from the participants' perspectives. Husserl's approach focuses on the essence of experiences, while Heidegger's emphasizes the interpretation of being and existence. The primary goal of phenomenological research is to understand how individuals perceive and interpret a particular phenomenon (Haven & Van Grootel, 2019).

Likewise, researchers engage in "epoché" or bracketing to set aside their own preconceptions and biases, ensuring that the findings genuinely reflect the participants' experiences. Data collection typically involves in-depth interviews, though other methods such as observations, diaries, and written narratives may also be used to gather rich, detailed descriptions. The analysis process involves reading and re-reading the data, identifying significant statements or phrases, clustering these into themes, and synthesizing the themes to articulate the core meaning or essence of the phenomenon. The final report provides a detailed and vivid description of the participants' experiences, offering profound insights into the phenomenon being studied. In some cases, researchers seek feedback from participants to validate the findings, ensuring accurate representation of their experiences (Pearse, 2019).

Furthermore, phenomenological research offers several advantages, making it a powerful tool for exploring human experiences. By prioritizing participants' perspectives, it captures the richness and complexity of individual experiences, allowing researchers to delve

deeply into subjective realities. This approach provides a nuanced understanding that can reveal underlying patterns and themes not immediately apparent through other research methods. Thus, the emphasis on detailed, vivid descriptions helps to convey the depth of participants' experiences, fostering empathy and a deeper appreciation of the studied phenomenon. This rich data can be invaluable for informing practices and interventions in fields such as education, psychology, and healthcare, where understanding individual experiences can lead to more effective and personalized approaches (Greening, 2019).

Participants

This study's participants were five (5) Datu Dumagkal Danial Elementary School teachers. Purposive sampling was the method used in the survey to choose the participants. Purposive sampling is a qualitative research technique that selects and finds circumstances that hold vital information to effectively use the limited resources available (Campbell et al., 2020). Finding and choosing people or organizations with substantial knowledge or experience on the topic of interest was required.

Inclusion Criteria. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling method. The participants needed to be teachers implementing positive discipline, male or female, aged 18-60, at Datu Dumagkal Danial Elementary School.

Exclusion Criteria. The scope of this study was limited to teachers exploring the implementation of positive discipline among learners. Teachers not involved in such programs were excluded from the study. Furthermore, the study focused on Datu Dumagkal Danial elementary school teachers above 18 and under 60 years of age. Retired teachers were also excluded from this study. By focusing on teachers, this study aimed to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences, insights, and challenges teachers faced in implementing positive discipline. This study focused on teachers' experiences and challenges in implementing positive discipline in their classrooms. Participants are aged 18-60, which excluded retired teachers. Teachers with less than one year of experience were also excluded. The study provided insights into teachers' challenges in implementing positive discipline.

Withdrawal Criteria. Throughout the investigation, the researcher informed the participants that they could leave the study without penalty. This ensured that participants were fully informed of their rights and could decline an invitation to join if they found it unpleasant or undesirable. They were not required to state their reason for withdrawal.

Data Collection

Qualitative research interviews aimed to gain insights into participants' perspectives and the meaning of their experiences, shedding light on their lived realities without imposing scientific explanations (McMullin, 2023). In this research, I served as the primary data collector, recognizing the importance of accurate data collection for maintaining research integrity. I carefully selected appropriate data collection instruments, whether pre-existing, modified, or newly developed, ensuring clear usage instructions to minimize data collection errors.

Before commencing the study, the researcher sought ethical clearance from the Ethics Research Committee (ERC) to ensure the moral conduct of the research. Upon approval, I obtained permission from the Dean and the Schools Division Superintendent of General Santos City, Sir Romelito G. Flores, CESO V, to proceed with the study. Participants were then approached and provided with Informed Consent Forms, ensuring their understanding and voluntary participation. Once participants had granted consent, the researcher conducted interviews via Zoom and in person, adhering to COVID-19 safety protocols. Recognizing the significance of building rapport and trust with participants, I initiated preliminary meetings to explain the study's details and assure participants of confidentiality.

I conducted one-on-one interviews at convenient times and locations for participants, recorded them digitally, and later transcribed the recordings. During the interviews, open-ended questions encouraged participants to share their experiences freely, while probing questions sought specific details. The interviews were conducted in a conducive, uninterrupted environment and lasted approximately an hour each.

Leading questions were posed at the end of interviews, although these typically yielded little information. All interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim by the researcher, and validated through member checking. Confidentiality was assured as outlined in the informed consent form. To lessen possible interruptions, the researcher's documentation on non-verbal cues or aspects were not captured in the audio.

The team quickly transcribed the audio recordings of the interviews and utilized member verification to ensure the data's accuracy. The participants attested to the interview transcripts by signature. Saturation, the point at which no new insights emerged, was determined based on recurrent themes and experiences expressed throughout the interviews.

Data Analysis

Qualitative research used surveys with open-ended questions or loosely structured interviews to uncover how people think and feel in certain situations, such as becoming a first-time father or undergoing chemotherapy. A researcher can apply Colaizzi's seven steps to analyze the data collected in a survey or interview.

In the first step, I read a description of each person participating in the study to understand the participants. Next, I extracted significant

statements to the research question, such as descriptions of how a first-time father feels about caring for a newborn. The critical statements should be direct quotations from the participants to reflect the research data accurately. The researcher explains the relevant sentences before drawing themes from the meanings to examine them. I categorized related and classified related concepts into groupings. I then revisited each participant to confirm the findings after incorporating the findings into a thorough topic description (Mishra et al., 2019).

Discussions in qualitative studies need to specify the steps in analyzing various forms of data. Analyzing text and different data types is a complex undertaking for qualitative researchers. It also entails organizing the data, performing a preliminary database read-through, coding and grouping themes, displaying the data, and formulating an interpretation (Maxwell, 2022).

Transcribing. While transcription is frequently regarded as a data collection component, it is also an analysis act. When I manually transcribed an interview, for example, I decided to convert the audio recording into text, shaping my analysis.

My methodology and objectives influenced this choice, and I should acknowledge it as part of my analysis process. When I worked with participants to discuss sensitive topics, occurs in a cross-cultural environment, or the documentation must be translated into another language, planning and communicating the transcription process becomes even more challenging (Bergin, 2018).

Coding. Codes give symbolic meaning to descriptive or inferential data gathered during a study. They are typically assigned to data "chunks" or "units" of varying sizes and can be simple, descriptive labels or more evocative and complex labels. A code is a researcher-generated construct in qualitative data analysis that symbolizes or translates data and thus assigns interpreted meaning to each datum for later purposes of pattern detection, categorization, assertion or proposition development, theory building, and other analytic processes (Chambers, 2018).

Categorizing. A category is formed by grouping codes related to one another due to their content or context. In other words, I classified codes as belonging to a category when they described different aspects, similarities, or differences in the text's content. When many codes resulted from the analysis, it could be helpful to assimilate smaller groups of closely related codes into sub-categories. Sub-categories related to one another by their content can then be formed into categories. A category answers questions about who, what, when, and where. Categories, in other words, are an expression of manifest content or what is visible in the data. The category names are accurate and brief (Assarroudi et al., 2018).

Formulating themes. The theme is an organized answer to the research question based on facts. It is a more ethereal concept that calls for more interpretation and information integration. As a researcher, I must familiarize myself with the data I collected before analyzing individual items and thoroughly understanding the collected data (Bergin, 2018). The first step in formulating themes involved taking notes and reviewing the collected data. After familiarizing the data, the next step was coding the data. It assigned or highlighted sentences from the interview and labels to describe the data's content (Kiger & Varpio, 2020).

After identifying the patterns in the collected data, it was time to generate themes. The current step in selecting which codes to keep and which to reject. After discovering themes, I reviewed the topics to ensure data accuracy, applicability, and value. Defining and naming a theme is the final step in the process. To comprehend the data, I must identify a precise list of themes.

Reporting. The last stage is to write up the results' description and final analysis. The writing process has already begun in some ways. Initial steps included taking notes, describing themes, and selecting representative data extracts. The final report should go beyond simply describing codes and themes (Kiger & Varpio, 2020).

In reporting, organizing all the ideas into a coherent narrative is vital. The central idea or category must have a strong explanatory power. The report should weave a narrative that explains how a researcher interprets the data and why their choice of themes and interpretation was made. The data are essential and correct.

The analysis should describe the data and provide context using narrative descriptions and representative data extracts to argue why the researcher's explanation is rich and comprehensive in answering the research question. Any direct data extracts should include sufficient context to understand their meaning and be accompanied by an interwoven textual description that explains their significance (Assarroudi et al., 2018).

Ethical Considerations

Voluntary Participation. The participants were free to participate without fear of consequences, loss of benefits, or compensation plans. Therefore, the participant's rights to contribute to the knowledge body were carefully considered and anticipated once the participant had been informed of the study's goal and received assistance from it. The subjects in this study were not coerced into taking part. Individuals who become uncomfortable while doing the survey can end their participation.

Privacy and confidentiality. Both confidentiality and privacy. Participants' privacy rights shall not be violated without their informed agreement following the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards this fundamental human right. Allowing respondents to omit their names from the survey questionnaire is one technique to maintain privacy and confidentiality in this quantitative study. In addition, confidentiality and privacy were preserved by withholding the informants' personal information, such as their age, gender, occupation, and health conditions. As a result, their identity was kept private for security reasons. Their answers to the survey

questionnaire were kept confidential and treated as such.

The informed consent process. Given the study's limitations, the potential research participants were adequately informed of the study's goals, procedures, and advantages in the most detailed way conceivable. The fact that the participants' permission was requested demonstrates that their participation was freely given. It was done in writing, outlining all the pertinent information that had to be provided to the participants and the methodology used to conduct the survey. There was no need for parental permission because the participants were consenting adults. The participants' identities were not listed on the survey form, and their responses were kept private.

Recruitment. The respondents were informed of why they had become part of the study. I communicated the study's goal to the participants so that they could further extrapolate from it and grasp its main points. In addition to the letter, I explained the background of the study and its importance.

Risks. This research determined if the benefit-risk ratio was acceptable and positive. This study's need to protect the participants from significant harm was equally essential. The study prioritized the welfare of the respondents. Furthermore, the participants were not harmed since their identity was held confidential. Their security and safety were of the utmost concern. As the researcher, I needed to ensure that the participants were physically, emotionally, and socially ready. I answered the survey questionnaire and confirmed that the participants did not feel discomfort or awkwardness.

Benefits. Implementing positive discipline in classrooms benefits the Department of Education, School Division Superintendents, and teachers. It enhances academic achievement, promotes inclusive education, and fosters a positive school climate. School leaders experience improved school atmospheres, while teachers enjoy reduced disruptions and enhanced student-teacher relationships. Overall, positive discipline initiatives contribute to creating thriving educational environments supporting all stakeholders' success.

Plagiarism. There was no hint or proof that the research had misinterpreted someone else's work. The study was checked for plagiarism using programs such as Grammarly. Cheerful character and integrity, linked to moral virtues and principles, are necessary for a researcher. I must know more about plagiarism to produce a respectable research report.

Fabrication. The study did not show or hint that what had been done had been intentionally misinterpreted. There was no deliberate drawing of incorrect inferences or fabrication of data or outcomes. Hence, I used theories relating to the data and other inferential notions.

Falsification. The study did not purposefully misrepresent the work to fit a model or theoretical expectation and had no evidence of overclaiming or exaggeration. This study did not conform to data manipulation, which included creating assertions or ignoring crucial information, moving materials, tools, or procedures to deceive others. The research process was transparent, and all data, methodologies, and findings were presented honestly and accurately, upholding the highest scientific rigor and ethical responsibility standards.

Conflict of Interest (COI). The study had no trace of conflict of interest. There was no sign of a conflict of interest in the study. For instance, there are circumstances in which professional judgment regarding the primary interest is required to disclose COI. A secondary incentive, such as monetary or academic rewards or reputation, often influences the participants' well-being or the research's reliability. In addition, the respondents were coerced into participating in the study by the researcher, who had no control or influence over them.

Deceit. There was no evidence that the research misled the participants about potential risks. Any investigation's participants' rights must be fiercely protected, especially if they have completed higher education; therefore, fair and acceptable standards must be followed. It entailed implementing protocols to minimize potential harm, allowing participants to withdraw consent or seek support if needed, and maintaining strict confidentiality to safeguard sensitive information.

Permission from Organization/Location. The researcher followed protocol for the study. Following approval from the panelists, adviser, and RMMCERC committee, I officially requested permission from the school division superintendent to survey through a letter. After that, I formalized the letter and mailed it to the school principals of the study's participating school.

Results

This phenomenological study describes the experiences of five public school teachers of Datu Dumagkal Danial Elementary School (DDDES) for the School Year 2022-2023. Additionally, it sought to answer how the participants describe the implementation of positive discipline. Likewise, this study aimed to answer the teachers' challenges in implementing positive discipline, how they cope with the difficulties in implementing positive discipline, and how implementing positive discipline impacts them as teachers. Lastly, this study also aimed to explore the similarities and differences between the cases of teachers implementing positive discipline.

Similarly, to protect the chosen participants' identities and privacy, each case was given code names such as Teacher 1, Teacher 2, Teacher 3, Teacher 4, and Teacher 5.

Description of Participants

Case 1—Teacher 1, a female Teacher of DDEES, has been teaching for four Months in the Department of Education.

Case 2 - Teacher 2, a female and Teacher 1, handling Grade 1 learners. She also has served the Department of Education for 12 years.

Case 3—Teacher 3, a female who assists Teacher 1 in handling Grade 5 learners, has been in service for 6 Years.

Case 4 - Teacher 4 a female, and Teacher 1, handling Grade 3 pupils. She has been in the service for 4 Years.

Case 5 - Teacher 5, a female and Teacher 1, handling Kindergarten. She has been in the service for 10 Years.

Categorization of Data

This part presents the analysis of themes through data categorization, including the challenges, coping mechanisms, and the insight learned by teachers in implementing positive discipline.

3.1. Challenges of the Participants in Implementing Positive Discipline in School Setting

The study found four (4) emergent themes in the participants' challenges in implementing positive discipline in a school setting. These are rigorous, Carrying out Strategies in the Classroom, Different perspectives, and Misbehaving Learners.

Rigorous. As public school teachers, participants were asked how they would describe the challenges in implementing positive discipline.

Teacher 1, a newly hired educator, expressed how difficult it was for her to instill positive discipline in her students. She said:

Bilang isang public teacher, ang pagpapatupad ng positive discipline ay hindi madaling gawain, lalo na para sa isang bagong guro tulad ko. Araw-araw, pinagsisikapan kong mahanap kung paano turuan ang mga mag-aaral sa paraang may disiplina at good moral values, bukod sa mga impormasyon na makukuha mula sa mga aklat (P 1, lines 4-8).

Implementing positive discipline is challenging as a public school teacher, especially as a newly hired teacher. Every day, I strive to figure out how to teach pupils in a way that they have discipline and good moral values aside from purely information from the book.

Teacher 2 emphasized the importance of mastering the art of disciplining learners inside the classroom. She shared:

As a public teacher, ang pag-iimplement ng positive discipline ay isang mahabang proseso at kailangan mamaster ang pagdidisiplina sa mga mag-aaral sa loob ng silid-aralan. Sa pag-iimplement ng positive discipline, ito ay maaaring magbigay ng magandang pananaw sa paraan ng pagdidisiplina sa isang bata; ito ay isang comprehensive way na gumagamit ng disiplina upang turuan at hindi parusa sa mga bata. Magiging mas comfortable at bukas ang mga bata kapag ginagamit ko ang positive discipline (P2, lines 101-107).

As a public school teacher, implementing positive discipline is a long process, and one needs to master disciplining the learners inside the classroom. Implementing positive discipline can result in a good outlook on disciplining a child. It is a comprehensive approach that uses discipline to teach rather than punish children. When I use positive discipline, children will feel at home and open.

For Teacher 3, the challenge lay in responding to positive discipline in the classroom. She explained:

"Bilang isang public teacher, medyo mahirap ang pagrespond sa positive discipline sa pagtuturo dahil ito ay nangangailangan ng iyong pasensya at pag-unawa sa bawat sitwasyon na maaaring mangyari sa klase. Kailangan mong ipakita ang kalmado mong pag-uugali sa bawat pangyayari na maaaring magkaroon sa klase lalo na pagdating sa pag-uugali ng mga mag-aaral". (P3, lines 182-186).

Responding to positive discipline is challenging for a public school teacher because it requires patience and understanding in every situation in class. You must show calmness in every situation that may arise in class, especially regarding learners' behavior.

Teacher 4 confessed that dealing with her emotions was one of the most challenging aspects. She stated:

Medyo mahirap at challenging. Kailangan kong kontrolin ang aking galit; naniniwala ako na normal na feeling ito kapag ang mga mag-aaral ay hindi nakikinig. Ngunit dahil sa pagpapatupad ng positive discipline, mas mahigpit kong sinusunod ang disiplinang ito (P 4, lines 287-290).

It is challenging. I need to control my anger; it is a normal feeling when your learners are not listening. However, I follow this discipline because of the implementation of positive discipline.

Teacher 5, who taught Kindergarten pupils, shared her unique challenge. She said:

Ang challenge sa pagpapatupad ng positive discipline bilang isang public teacher, lalo na sa pagtuturo sa mga mag-aaral sa Kindergarten, ay ang pagiging "neutral" o ang pagkakaroon ng self-control (P 5, lines 362-364).

The challenge in implementing positive discipline as a public school teacher, especially in teaching Kindergarten pupils, is "neutral" Or having self-control.

Carrying out of Strategies in the Classroom. Participants were asked on their most challenging experience that they have encountered, and this was implementing positive discipline and how it changed them as public servants.

Sa palagay ko, ang magkaibang pagpapalaki ng mga mag-aaral ang nagiging mas mahirap na ipatupad ang positive discipline. Nahahirapan akong gamitin ang tiyak na teknik at strategy dahil hindi ito para sa lahat. Ito ay nagpapaliwanag sa akin na maglaan ng karagdagang pagsisikap bilang isang public servant upang magkaroon ng mas malawak at mas malalim na pag-unawa at pasensya sa aking mga mag-aaral (P 1, lines 11-16).

The pupils' different upbringings make it more challenging to implement positive discipline. I need help using specific techniques and strategies since they are only for some. It made me realize that I need to make an extra effort as a public servant to have a broader and deeper understanding and patience with my pupils.

Para sa akin, ang pinakamahirap na naranasan ko sa pa-implement ng positive discipline ay ang pagtuturo kaysa sa pagpaparusa, lalo na sa mga behavioral problem ng aking mga mag-aaral. It changes me dahil binigyan ko ng self-control at pinalawak ang aking pasensya at pag-unawa sa kilos ng aking mga estudyante (P 2, lines 110-114).

For me, the biggest challenge I encountered in implementing positive discipline was to teach rather than punish, especially with the behavioral problems of my learners. It changed me because I gained self-control and widened my patience and understanding of my pupils' behavior.

Disruptive behavior ay ang pinakamahirap na karanasan na aking naranasan sa klase, at nagiging mahirap sa akin na mag-concentrate. Ito ay nagdulot sa akin ng stress, ngunit kailangan kong maging mahinahon at ipakita ang aking pagmamahal at ipatupad ang positive discipline. Ngunit may mga pagkakataon na nawawala ang aking pasensya at pinagsasabihan ko sila sa harap ng kanilang mga kaklase. Sa bandang huli, napagtanto ko na marahil nababagot ang mga mag-aaral sa aralin o hindi nila ito naiintindihan. Ito ay nagbago sa aking perspective in teaching na dapat kong umangkop sa paghahatid ng aking approach batay sa kanilang interest (P3, lines 189-197).

Disruptive behavior is the most challenging experience I have encountered in class, making it difficult to concentrate. It caused me stress, but I had to be calm, show my warmth, and impose positive discipline. However, there were moments when I lost my temper and scolded them in front of their classmates. Moreover, in the end, I realized that these learners may get bored with the lesson or need help understanding it. It changes my perspective on teaching, and I also have to adjust the delivery of my approach based on their interest.

Kapag kailangan mong ituwid ang unacceptable behavior ng iyong mag-aaral sa tamang paraan, ito ay nagpapakita kung gaano ka kagaling na disciplinarian at kung gaano ka kaeffective bilang isang guro sa pagpapatibay ng positive way ng pagdidisiplina sa mga mag-aaral (4, lines 293-296).

When you correct your student's unacceptable behavior in the right way, it reflects on your quality as a disciplinarian and your effectiveness as a teacher in reinforcing positive ways of disciplining students.

The most challenging experience na aking naranasan ay kapag mayroon kang mag-aaral na may special needs, particularly sa mga mag-aaral na may dawn syndrome at ADHD. Dahil hindi mo alam kung anong strategy ang gagamitin para e discipline ang mga bata na may pangangailangan. Maraming pagkakataon na kailangan kong magkaroon ng malalim na pasensya at mas maraming pag-unawa sa kanilang kalagayan (P 5, lines 367-372).

The most challenging experience I encountered was when I had a pupil with special needs, specifically Down's syndrome and ADHD pupils. Because you need to know what strategy you will use to discipline children with needs, there were many chances where I had much patience and a greater understanding of their condition.

Different Perspective. Participants were asked about the advantages and disadvantages of implementing positive discipline.

Teacher 1 shared:

In proper implementation, tiyak na magkakaroon ng malaking epekto sa mga mag-aaral ang positive discipline. Sa pamamagitan nito, maaari tayong maging effective at trusted na teacher. Bukas ang komunikasyon ng mga mag-aaral sa kanilang guro. Bilang guro, maipapakilala natin ang bawat personality at aalagaan sila, ngunit sa realidad, kahit gaano pa kagusto na ipatupad ito, talagang mahirap ang pagpapatupad ng positive discipline, lalo na't nahaharap ako sa magkakaibang uri ng mga mag-aaral, at ito ay may kaugnayan sa uri ng disiplina na ibinibigay sa kanila sa tahanan ng kanilang mga tagapangalaga (P 1, lines 19-27).

Proper implementation of positive discipline will significantly impact pupils. Through it, we can be effective and efficient teachers. Pupils will openly communicate with the teacher. As teachers, we can recognize every personality they have nourished. However, as much as we want to implement positive discipline, it is challenging, especially when I encounter diverse learners. It has to do with the type of discipline they have at home by their guardians.

Teacher 2 expressed:

Isa sa mga advantages sa pag implement ng positive discipline ay nagiging malakas and aking self-control sa mga bata, nakakatuto ang mga bata sap ag respeto at pagiging responsableng mga bata. Ang nakikita kong disadvantage ay marami ring mga bata ang hindi kaagad nakaka intindi sa, they sometimes abuse your treatment to them that's why they repeat the mistake (P2, lines 117-121).

One of the advantages of implementing positive discipline is that it strengthens my self-control with children. Children learn to respect and become responsible individuals. However, one disadvantage I see is that some children do not immediately understand and sometimes abuse the leniency, leading them to repeat their mistakes.

Teacher 3 revealed the difficulty in handling disruptive behavior in the classroom, causing stress and difficulty concentrating. She stated:

Para sa akin, ang advantage sa positive discipline ay respect sa karapatan ng mga mag-aaral sa healthy development, protection mula sa karahasan, at active participation sa kanilang pag-aaral. Ngunit may mga disadvantage din ito. Halimbawa, kung ang bata ay gumawa ng seryosong paglabag na nagdulot ng pinsala sa kanyang kaklase. Ang karahasan na ito ay seryoso at hindi sapat ang positive discipline para harapin ang ganitong uri ng hindi responsableng pag-uugali (P 3, lines 200-206).

The advantage of implementing positive discipline is that it respects learners' right to healthy development, protection from violence, and active participation in their education. Moreover, this disadvantage is that it is only appropriate in some situations. For example, if the child commits a serious violation that causes his classmate an injury. This violence is severe enough that positive discipline alone cannot handle such irresponsible behavior.

Another teacher shared her perspective on the significance of correcting unacceptable behavior correctly. She reflected:

Ang ilan sa mga advantage ay to strengthen the bond sa pagitan ng mga guro at mga mag-aaral, pagtulong sa mga mag-aaral na kilalanin ang mga acceptable at hindi acceptable na pag-uugali, at pagtulong sa kanila na maging mabuting mag-aaral. Sa kabilang banda, ang mga disadvantage ay kapag ito ay hindi naiimplement nang mali, na nagdulot ng negative effect sa mga mag-aaral at kapag ikaw ay sobrang mahigpit sa iyong mga mag-aaral, lalo na kung rebellious sila (P 4, lines 299-305).

Some advantages are strengthening the bond between teachers and students, helping students acknowledge acceptable and unacceptable behavior, and helping them be good students. On the other hand, the disadvantages are when it is implemented incorrectly. It hurts students, and also, when you are being strict with your students, especially somehow, they will be rebellious.

Finally, Teacher 5 narrated the most challenging experience dealing with students with special needs, such as those with Down's Syndrome and ADHD. She emphasized:

Ang advantage ng pagpapatupad ng positive discipline ay ito'y maaaring gabayin o pamahalaan ang mga mag-aaral upang maiwasan ang hindi mabuting pag-uugali sa silid-aralan. Ang kanilang masamang mga ugali ay magiging pagbabago rin. Gayunpaman, ang disadvantages nito ay nagiging sanhi ng pagiging strict ng guro sa loob ng silid-aralan nang walang pantay na pagmamahal at pagmamahal na maaaring magdulot ng pagiging matigas at mapanghimagsik na pag-uugali". (P5, lines 375-381).

The advantage of implementing positive discipline is guiding or managing pupils away from misbehaving in the classroom. Their bad habits will also be changed. However, the disadvantage is when a teacher has strict rules inside her room without equal love and affection, which can trigger defiant and rebellious behavior.

Misbehaving Learners. Participants were asked how these experiences affected them as public school teachers.

For Teacher 1, the challenges brought about by the stress and occasional burnout served as motivation to strive harder and contribute more as a teacher in a public school. She stated:

Ang mga challenges para sa akin ay ang labis na pagka-stressful at kung minsan ay nararanasan ko ang pagkaburn out, ngunit ito ay nagbibigay-sigla sa akin upang mas pagsikapan na maging mas magaling at mag-ambag bilang isang guro sa pampublikong paaralan (P 1, lines 31-34).

The challenge for me is that it is very stressful, and sometimes, I experience burnout, but this motivates me to strive more to become a better public teacher.

Teacher 2 expressed how the challenging experiences affected her positively. She said:

As a school teacher, the challenging experiences affect me, ang paraan kung paano ko mapananatiling mahinahon sa mga sitwasyon at eencourage ang aking mga mag-aaral sa mas mabuting pag-uugali ay nagpapaligaya at nagpapalakas sa akin. Ipinagmamalaki ko ang pagbabago na nagagawa ko sa kanila sa pamamagitan ng positive discipline (P2, lines 124-128).

As a school teacher, challenging experiences affect me. How I handled situations calmly and encouraged my pupils to behave better makes me happy and proud because I change them through positive discipline.

However, for Teacher 3, the challenges had a more personal effect. She elaborated:

Minsan, ito ay nakakaapekto sa aking moral values bilang isang public teacher. Kinakailangan ang iyong pasensya upang maunawaan at mabalanse ang iba't ibang pangangailangan sa learnings ng mga mag-aaral. Bilang isang guro, mahalaga na maging flexible sa pagbabago ng mga plano upang mawala ang pagkagambala ng normal na takbo ng klase.(P3, lines 209-213).

Sometimes, it affects my moral values as a public teacher. It takes patience to grasp unexpected situations and balance the different learning needs of the learners. As a teacher, it is essential to be flexible in rearranging plans to disrupt the routine.

Teacher 4, both a teacher and a mother, shared the difficulty of implementing positive discipline for all students, as they did not adapt well. She shared:

Bilang isang guro at the same time a mother, mahirap ipatupad ang positive discipline sa lahat ng iyong mag-aaral dahil hindi lahat sa kanila ay nakaka-adapt dito at hindi ito effective para sa kanilang pag-uugali. Kailangan mong unahing suriin ang pag-uugali ng iyong mag-aaral bago ito ipatupad (P 4, lines 308-311).

As a teacher and a mother, it is difficult to implement positive discipline for all your students because some of them cannot adapt to it, and it is not adequate for their behavior. You first need to assess your students' behavior before implementing it.

For teacher 5, the aftermath of the pandemic had its toll. She expressed:

After pandemic... Napakahalagang hamon ang pag-handle ng maraming bilang ng mga mag-aaral, at ang submission at workloads ang nagdadala ng stress at burnout... Kulang na pagsasanay. Lalo na sa pag-handle ng mga mag-aaral na may special needs (P5, lines 384-387).

After the pandemic, I was significantly challenged by handling many pupils, the submissions and workloads that contributed to stress, burnout, and inadequate training—especially handling pupils with special needs.

Participants were asked how they felt when facing different challenges in implementing positive discipline and how it affected their physical and emotional well-being.

Teacher 1, a newly hired teacher, expressed the exhaustion she felt, both physically and mentally. She said:

Paminsan-minsan nakakapagod physically at mentally. May mga pagkakataon na nawawalan nan ang gana at nawawala ang aking pagmamahal sa pagtuturo ng mga batang mag-aaral dahil hindi ako gaanong mahigpit sa kanila. Bilang isang bagong guro, kailangan ko pang magsanay ng marami upang mapabuti ang aking disiplina (P 1, lines 38-42).

It is physically and mentally exhausting sometimes. Some moments demotivated me and made me lose my passion for teaching young learners because I was not strict with them. As a newly hired teacher, it takes much practice to improve my discipline.

Teacher 2, however, found a motherly role in implementing positive discipline. She expressed:

In implementing positive discipline, naranasan kong maging parang isang ina sa aking 40 na mga mag-aaral. Sa halip na parusahan sila na magiging sanhi ng takot sa kanila, sila'y aking pinupuri at binibigyan ng oras na magkasama para maengganyo sa tamang pag-uugali (P 2, lines 132-135).

In implementing positive discipline, I experienced motherhood to my 40 pupils. Instead of punishing them by making them frightened, I encouraged them by praising them and spending quality time together.

For Teacher 3, dealing with the different abilities and behaviors of the learners proved challenging. She noted that the need to address disruptive behavior repeatedly impacts her energy levels, diminishes her motivation, and causes stress. She shared:

Ang pag-handle sa iba't ibang kakayahan at kapasidad ng mga mag-aaral ay hindi madali. Kailangan mong harapin sila nang magkaiba. Isa sa mga kadahilanan sa paggawa nito ng mahirap ay ang degree ng kanilang pag-uugali sa klase. At hindi mo mabilis na marespond ito sa positive discipline dahil paulit-ulit na mga disruptive behavior. Bilang isang guro, ito ay nakakaapekto sa degree ng iyong energy, at ito ay makakasira ng iyong araw. Minsan, nababawasan nito ang aking motibasyon sa trabaho at nagdudulot ng stress sa akin (P 3, lines 217-223).

Handling the different abilities and capacities of the learners is a challenge. You have to deal with them differently. Furthermore, one of the factors that makes it difficult is the degree of their behavior in class. Moreover, you need to respond more quickly to positive discipline because disruptive behavior is done repeatedly. As a teacher, it affects your energy level and will ruin your day. Sometimes, it reduces my motivation to work and causes me stress.

In Teacher 4, self-doubt and frustration took a toll on her. She often questioned herself, wondering if she was a good teacher and an effective disciplinarian, which led to increased stress. She said:

Personally, I got frustrated. Madaling nagtatanong sa sarili kung ako ba ay isang magaling na guro. Ako ba ay isang effective na disciplinarian? Somehow, ito ay nagiging sanhi ng stress sa akin (P4, lines 315-317).

I get frustrated. I quickly questioned myself: Am I a good teacher? Am I an effective disciplinarian? Somehow, it caused me stress.

Lastly, Teacher 5 shared the difficulty of disciplining children with diverse behaviors and languages, especially when they were not her children or relatives. She stated that it was challenging to understand and address the unique needs of each child. She stated:

Sa simula, syempre, mahirap ito. Mahirap disiplinahin ang mga bata na may iba't ibang pag-uugali at wika, lalo na kapag hindi sila iyong mga anak o kamag-anak mo. Paano ito nakakaapekto? Maaring magdulot ito ng physical stress at mentally absent (P 5, lines 391-394).

First, it is challenging to discipline children with different behaviors and languages, even more so when they are not your children or relatives. How does it affect you? Well, physically stressed and mentally absent.

Teacher 5's experiences disciplining children with diverse behaviors and languages, particularly when they are not her children or relatives, underscore educators' significant challenges. Her reflections highlight the physical and mental toll such responsibilities can impose, indicating a need for strategies and support systems to assist teachers in managing these complex classroom dynamics effectively.

Table 1. *Challenges of the participants in implementing positive discipline in a school setting*

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Is not an easy task.	Rigorous
Is a long process.	
Needs to master the disciplining.	
Is quite challenging.	Carrying out of Strategies in the classroom
Difficulty in dealing students from different backgrounds and with varying needs.	
Maintaining focus in the classroom was stressful.	
The challenges of identifying and implementing effective discipline strategies.	
Maintaining bond while enforcing discipline.	Different perspectives
Limitation of positive discipline to student with special needs.	
Striking the right balance between being firm with discipline and showing compassion towards students.	
Disruptive behavior	Misbehaving Learners

3.2. Coping Mechanism of the Participants in Implementing Positive Discipline in the School Setting

To answer this research question, I thoroughly interviewed five informants and conducted a focus group discussion. Several sub-questions were asked to explore the coping mechanisms of teachers exploring their positive discipline in their experiences. Several emergent themes were identified: Teacher Mentoring, Balancing Kindness and Firmness, Positive reinforcement, and Proactive Behavior Support.

Teacher Mentoring. Participants were asked how they handled their challenges in implementing positive discipline. They were also asked how effective those strategies were in handling the challenges.

Teacher 1 emphasized the importance of seeking professional advice and help. She explained:

Mahalaga na humingi ng professional advice at tulong. Tunay na mahalaga na magtanong ng mga strategy mula sa mga mas nakatatanda o may alam lalo na't bago pa lang ako sa larangang ito. Marami akong kailangang matutunan at kailangang kalimutan (P1, lines 45-48).

It is crucial to get expert counsel and help and to ask for strategies from my seniors or those who are knowledgeable, especially since I am new to this field. I have so much to learn and unlearn.

Teacher 2 proudly acknowledged that positive discipline effectively promotes good behavior among students while preventing negative and risky behaviors. She said:

Ito ay nagpo-promote ng positive discipline sa mga mag-aaral habang pinipigilan ang mga nnegative at mga risky na pag-uugali, at oo! Ang positive discipline ay effective (P2, lines 138-140).

Positive discipline promotes positive student behavior while preventing negative and risky behaviors, and yes, it is indeed effective.

Balancing Kindness and Firmness. Teacher 3 believed in finding a balance between kindness and firmness. She answered:

I think, dapat maging mabait at matibay ako sa pagpapatupad ng positive discipline. Kung labis akong mag-concentrate sa pagiging mabait, mahihirapan akong harapin ang problemang ito. Ang dapat na diskarte ay maging mabait/mahinahon at sabay na matibay, hangga't ito'y may paggalang. Ito ay napakaeffective dahil alam nila ang kanilang mga limitasyon at sila'y kumikilala sa kanilang mga pagkakamali (P3, lines 226-231).

I had to be both kind and firm in implementing positive discipline. If I concentrated so hard on kindness, it would be difficult for me to deal with this problem. The approach would be kind/calm, and firm as long as it is respectful. It is very effective because they know their limitations and are aware of their mistakes.

Teacher 4 shared that they consistently allocated time for prayer and searched for positive discipline strategies suitable for their students' behaviors. She replied:

Naglalaan ako palagi ng oras upang manalangin at hanapin ang mga positive discipline strategy na angkop sa pag-uugali ng aking mga mag-aaral (P 4, lines 320-321).

I always find time to pray and research positive discipline strategies that are appropriate for my student's behavior.

Lastly, Teacher 5 discussed the challenges of staying neutral during conflicts and identifying the root cause of misbehavior. She said:

Ang mga challenges na aking naranasan sa pag-implement ng positive discipline ay ang manatiling neutral sa panahon ng mga alitan at hanapin ang root cause ng misbehavior. Oo (o marahil), ito ay epektibo sa pamamagitan ng pagbibigay sa kanila ng pagkakataon na mag-isip at magbigay ng pagmamahal sa mga mag-aaral na may maling pag-uugali (P 5, lines 397-401).

The challenges I have encountered in implementing positive discipline were remaining neutral during conflicts and searching for the root cause of misbehavior. Yes (or maybe), giving them time to think and giving some love to misbehaving pupils is practical.

Proactive Behavior Support. Participants were asked what strategies they had employed in dealing with the difficulties in implementing positive discipline. They were also asked why they chose to use those strategies to cope with the disadvantages of implementing positive discipline.

Teacher 1 shared how blessed she was to have a supportive Master Teacher who gave her ideas and wisdom. She stated:

I was so blessed dahil ang aking Master Teacher ay napakalapit sa akin. Nakakuha ako ng mga ideya at knowledge mula sa kanya. Everything takes time lalo na sa pakikitungo sa iba't ibang pag-uugali ng mga bata, kailangan kong palakasin ang aking pasensya sa aking mga mag-aaral. Ito ay isang proseso ng pagbibigayan kung saan dapat kong praktisin ang aking pagiging matibay nang hindi nagsasagawa ng negative discipline. I pray for the soul's ng aking mga mag-aaral at ang aking wisdom (P 1, lines 52-58).

I was so blessed because my Master Teacher was very hands-on with me. I gained ideas and wisdom from her. Everything takes time, especially dealing with children's different behaviors. I need to strengthen my patience with my learners. It is a give-and-take process. I should practice my firmness without implementing negative discipline. I prayed for the souls of my children and my wisdom.

Teacher 2 succeeded in two simple yet powerful strategies - listening to her students and encouraging them towards better behavior. She explained:

Ang mga strategy na ginamit ko upang harapin ang mga suliranin sa positive discipline ay ang pakikinig sa kanila at encourage them sa mas mabuting pag-uugali (P 2, lines 144-146).

I employed strategies to deal with the difficulties of positive discipline: I listened to them and encouraged them to behave better.

Teacher 3, a dedicated teacher, displayed a remarkable approach to handling distractions in the classroom. She said:

Dapat kong kontrolin ang aking galit at tanungin sila nang mahinahon kung ano ang nangyayari. Maari rin akong magtanong sa kanila kung may katanungan sila tungkol sa aralin. Ipaliwanag sa kanila na ang ingay ay maaaring maka-distract sa pagtuturo at proseso ng pag-iisip, at nakakadistract din ito sa kanilang mga kaklase. Ipapaalala sa kanila ang mga patakaran sa pakikinig at na sila mismo ang bahagi ng paggawa ng mga patakaran para sa klase. Sabihin ko sa kanila na maari nilang pag-usapan ang ibang paksa sa kanilang libreng oras o sa pagitan ng mga klase. Dapat kong maunawaan na ang ilang mga bata ay madaling ma-distract. Dapat ko ring intindihin na sila ay may iba't ibang interes at paraan ng pag-aaral. Ang iba ay mas mabilis matuto sa pamamagitan ng discussion, habang ang iba naman ay mas mahusay matuto sa pamamagitan ng mga activities. Dapat kong maunawaan na hindi palaging alam ng mga bata ang epekto ng kanilang mga kilos sa iba (P 3, lines 235-247).

I have to control my anger and ask them in a calm voice what is going on. I may also ask them if they have questions about the lesson. Explain to them that noise can distract your teaching and thinking process and that it is also distracting to their classmates. Remind them about the rules on listening and that they were part of creating them for the class. Tell them they can discuss other topics during their free time or between classes. I have to understand that some children can be easily distracted. I also have to know that they have different interests and learning styles. Some learn faster through discussion, while some learn better through activities. Children may only sometimes be aware of the effect of their actions on others.

In her quest to instill positive discipline, Teacher 4 embraced open communication. She answered:

I encourage communication. Nagkakaroon ako ng heart to heart nap ag-uusap sa aking mag-aaral. Tinatanong ko siya kung bakit at ano ang kanyang ginawa. Kinikilala ko ang kanyang mabuti at masamang pag-uugali at tinutulungan siya na maunawaan ang kanyang mga kilos(P4, lines 325-328).

I encourage communication—heart-to-heart talks with my student, asking him why and what he did. I acknowledge his good and bad behavior and help him realize his actions.

Finally, Teacher 5 emphasized the importance of fairness, positivity, and equality in her approach to discipline. She stated:

Ang mga strategy ay ang maging fair, positive, at may pagkakapantay-pantay; kilalanin ang iyong mga mag-aaral at ipakita sa kanila na nagmamalasakit ka...Pakinggan sila, bigyan sila ng atensyon, at bigyang halaga ang kanilang mabubuting gawain". (P 5, lines 405-408).

The strategies are to be fair, positive, and consistent, get to know your pupils, and let them know you care, hear them out, give attention, and catch them being good.

Positive Reinforcement. Among the strategies they employed to deal with the difficulties in implementing positive discipline, they were asked what was the most effective. These perspectives highlight a range of techniques teachers use to promote positive discipline in the classroom, including seeking support from colleagues, offering encouragement, understanding individual student needs, maintaining privacy in communication, and demonstrating fairness, positivity, and consistency.

Teacher 1, a newly hired teacher, found solace in seeking advice from her colleagues. She elaborates:

Bilang isang bagong-hire na guro, ang pagtatanong sa aking mga colleagues ay talagang nagpapagaan sa aking mga problema. Nakakuha ako ng ilang mga ideya mula sa kanila na naging salamin ko sa pagpapatupad ng positive discipline." (P1, lines 61-64).

As a newly hired teacher, asking my colleagues eased my difficulties. They gave me some insights, eventually becoming my mirror in implementing positive discipline.

Teacher 2 discovered the power of encouragement as the best strategy for implementing positive discipline. She explained:

Encouragement ay ang pinakamahusay na paraan at strategy sa pagpapatupad ng positive discipline (P2, lines 149-150).

Encouragement is the best strategy for implementing positive discipline.

However, Teacher 3 understood that each student had unique interests and learning styles. She shared:

Ang pinakaeffective na paraan ay understand them na sila ay may iba't ibang interes at paraan ng pag-aaral. Kaya kailangan kong magbigay ng interactive discussions o mga activities na lahat ay makakasali (P 3, lines 250-252).

The most effective way to do this is to understand that they have different interests and learning styles. So, I have to provide interactive discussions and activities for everyone.

For Teacher 4, privacy was the key to effectiveness. She expressed:

Mas effective ito kung pag-uusapan privately, kausapin siya sa pinakarespetong paraan (P4, lines 331-332).

It is more effective if you communicate privately and talk to him in a respectful way.

Finally, Teacher 5 emphasized the value of fairness, positivity, and consistency. She stated:

Maging fair, positive, at magpakatatag, at ipaalam sa mga mag-aaral na nagmamalasakit ka. Sa mga strategy na aking pinili, kanilang matututunan ang tiwala sa kanilang sarili at baka pati na rin mabago ang kanilang pag-uugali (P5, lines 411-413).

Be Fair, positive, and consistent, and let the pupils know you care. With my chosen strategies, they will gain confidence/self-confidence and change their behavior.

Table 2. *Coping Mechanism of the participants in implementing positive discipline in the school setting*

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Seek professional advice and help.	Teacher Mentoring
Hands-on to give technical assistance.	
Both kind and firm.	Balancing kindness and firmness
Be kind and calm.	
Be firm.	
To listen and encourage them.	Positive reinforcement
Ask them in a calm voice.	
To understand different interests.	
Encourage communication.	Proactive Behavior Support
Promotes positive student behavior.	
Prevent negative and risky behaviors.	
Vary interests and learning styles.	
Provide interactive discussions or activities.	

3.3. Impact of the Participants in Implementing Positive Discipline in the School Setting

Researchers conducted a focus group discussion and an in-depth interview to answer this research question. Various sub-questions were asked to draw out the teachers' insights into a positive discipline that they could share based on their experiences. The study found

four (4) significant themes that emerged: teaching by heart, Patience and Understanding, Individualized Approach, and Gains.

Teaching by Heart. Participants were asked what insights or lessons they had learned in implementing positive discipline and how the lesson affected them.

Teacher 1 spoke with passion in her eyes. She said:

Nalaman ko na ang teaching ay hindi laging nakabatay sa libro kundi sa puso. Ang positive discipline ay nagbibigay ng big impact sa aking mga mag-aaral dahil mas nakakapagbigay ako ng pagmamalasakit sa kanilang puso at kaluluwa. Naniniwala ako na magiging positibong impluwensya ito sa kanilang buhay bilang isang indibidwal na lubos na mabubuo ang pagpapahalaga at asal (P1, lines 67-71).

I learned that teaching is not always teaching by the book but teaching with a heart. Positive discipline significantly impacts my learners because I tend to touch their hearts and souls. It will influence their lives as holistically developed individuals with values and manners.

Teacher 2 eagerly shared her experience. She shared:

Ang mga aral na natutunan ko pa-iimplement ng positive discipline ay ang pagkakaroon ng respect sa pagitan ng mga mag-aaral at mga guro, at ito ay magbubunga ng good relationship between sa mga mag-aaral at guro sa pamamagitan ng pagtutulungan at pagkasama-sama (P2, lines 153-156).

The lessons I have learned in implementing positive discipline is just having respect between pupils and teachers, and it will create a good relationship between learners and teachers by spending time together.

Teacher 3, with a sense of accomplishment, spoke next. She said:

I learned na ang pag-iimplement ng positive discipline ay makakatulong sa pagbuo ng self-control ng mga mag-aaral at tutulong sa kanilang paggawa ng matalinong mga desisyon. Bagamat kailangan ng pasensya, maingat na atensyon, cooperation, at mabuting pag-unawa sa mga mag-aaral, ito ay magtutulak sa kanila na maging mabuting mamamayan. Mahirap sa simula ngunit kapag nasanay ka na, mas madali na gawin ito. Ang mga learnings na ito ay nakakaapekto sa akin mentally sa pagharap sa pag-uugali ng mga bata (P 3, lines 255-261).

I learned that positive discipline could develop learners' self-control and help them make thoughtful choices. Though it requires patience, thoughtful attention, cooperation, and a good understanding of the learners, it allows them to be good citizens. It is hard initially, but when you are used to it, it will be easier for you to do it. These earnings affect my mindset when dealing with children's behavior.

As Teacher 4 shared her thoughts, she emphasized the importance of tailoring disciplinary strategies to each student's unique perspective. She answered:

May mga strategy in discipline na hindi angkop sa lahat ng mag-aaral dahil may iba't ibang pananaw sila tungkol dito. May ilan na maaaring magdamdam at mahiya, habang may iba naman na maaaring maging mas aggressive. Ito'y tungkol sa pagkakaroon ng sapat na kaalaman tungkol sa iyong mga mag-aaral at maging friendly sa bawat isa sa kanila nang may limitations at in authoritative way (P 4, lines 335-340).

Some discipline strategies are inappropriate for every student because they have different views about it; some will feel ashamed and embarrassed, and some will become more aggressive. It is about knowing your students well and being friendly to each one of them with limitations and authoritative ways.

Lastly, Teacher 5 highlighted the urgency of addressing wrongdoing promptly to prevent its replication. She explained:

Ang isang bata na nag commit ng wrongdoing ay dapat agad na mabigyan ng action at attention upang hindi ito tularan ng kanyang mga kaklase. Ito ay para masigurado na ang iyong aralin ay magiging mabilis at walang anumang abala habang ipinaliliwanag mo ang aralin (P 5, lines 416-419).

A child who has committed wrongdoing should have immediate action and attention so as not to be imitated by his classmates. For that, your lesson is smooth and without any disturbance while you are explaining the lesson.

Patience and Understanding. Participants were asked what benefits they had gained from implementing positive discipline.

Teacher 1, a seasoned teacher, stepped forward with a thoughtful expression. She admitted:

Para sa akin hindi Madali ang pag-iimplement ng positive discipline, but it helps me upang palawakin ang aking pananaw bilang isang guro at iwanan ang dating estilo ng disiplina. Nalaman ko na dapat kong e master ang pasensya at pag-unawa sa aking mga mag-aaral, kahit pa may iba't ibang kultura o relihiyon (P 1, lines 74-77).

Implementing positive discipline is not easy for me, but this helped me widen my perception as a teacher and let go of the old discipline style. I learned that I should master the patience and understanding of my learners, even with diverse cultures or religions.

Next, Teacher 2, with an air of contentment, shared her revelations. She said:

Ang mga benefits o lessons na natutunan ko sa pag-iimplement ng positive discipline is to realize na sa pagpapatupad nito ay makakamit natin ang maayos na pamamahala sa silid-aralan at magiging mapayapa ito dahil palaging ipinapakita at ipinapatupad ang positive discipline. (P 2, lines 159-162).

The benefits or lessons I have learned from implementing positive discipline are that we can manage our classrooms and make our classrooms peaceful because we always show and implement positive discipline.

Teacher 3, a soft-spoken teacher, spoke with conviction. She said:

The benefits I gained mula dito ay nagdadala ng kapayapaan, responsibilidad, at paggalang sa atmosphere sa loob ng silid-aralan o maaari ring dalhin ito sa lipunan which in turn can foster unity and love (P 3, lines 264-266).

The benefits I gained from this are that it brings peace, responsibility, and respect to the atmosphere inside the classroom, or they can bring in the society, which in turn can foster unity and love.

As for Teacher 4, her eyes sparkled with enthusiasm. She answered:

Una, Madali ang pakikipag-communicate sa aking mga mag-aaral nang walang hadlang. two Nakamit ko ang kanilang tiwala at respect. pangatlo Sila ay may takot sa pagkakamaling Gawain (P4, lines 343-345).

First, I easily communicate with my students without barriers; Second, I gain their trust and respect; Third, they have a fear of wrongdoing.

Lastly, Teacher 5, radiating warmth and wisdom, shared her transformative journey. She explained

I became fair sa aking mga kilos at tiniyakin na kapag ang aking mga mag-aaral ay nagkakaroon ng maling pag-uugali, agad ko silang ituwid in a positive way. Ang mga batang isipan ay kailangang ituwid at alagaan ng maayos dahil ang Kindergarten ay ang kanilang pundasyon sa kanilang pag-aaral at values formation (P 5, lines 422-426).

I acted fairly and ensured that whenever my learners misbehaved, I immediately corrected them. Young minds must be rectified and nurtured properly because Kindergarten is the foundation of their learning and values formation.

Gains. Participants were asked what benefits teachers and learners get from positive discipline. They were also asked in what way they thought it was beneficial.

Teacher 1, a wise and compassionate teacher, spoke with a gentle smile. She said:

Ang mga benefits na tinatamasa ng mga mag-aaral at guro mula sa positive discipline ay pagmamahal at pag-unawa sa damdamin ng isa't isa. Sila ay nakararamdam kapag ikaw ay galit o malungkot. Agad nilang iaayos ang kanilang mga kilos. Parang boomerang effect. Kapag hinawakan mo ang kanilang mga puso, hahawakan din nilaang sa iyo. Ang teaching ay higit pa sa pagtuturo lamang sa kanila kundi pagtulong sa kanila in lifting their souls at pagkakakilanlan (P 1, lines 80-85).

Positive discipline benefits learners and teachers by promoting love and understanding one's feelings. People tend to feel when they are mad or upset, and they immediately correct their actions. It is like a boomerang effect. When you touch their hearts, they will touch yours, too. Teaching is more than just teaching them; it is helping them lift their souls and individuality.

Teacher 2, with a glint of excitement in her eyes, shared her perspective. She stated:

Ang benefits sa pag-iimplement ng positive discipline ay ang pagkakaroon ng good relationship sa pagitan ng mga guro at mga mag-aaral, at mananatili sa puso ng aming mga mag-aaral ang mga salitang itinanim namin sa kanilang isipan (P 2, lines 165-168).

The benefits of implementing positive discipline are having a good relationship with the teachers and learners' relationship and remaining in the heart of our pupils the words that we teach in our minds.

Teacher 3, with a strong sense of purpose, emphasized the practical benefits of positive discipline. She explained:

Ito ay maaaring mag-reinforce sa kanilang good behavior at maalis ang undesirable behavior. Kung ang mga bata ay may sense of responsibility sa kanilang mga kilos, ang kanilang pag-aaral ay magiging kapaki-pakinabang sa kanila. Sila ay matututo nang walang pagkakaabala. Makakafocus sila sa kanilang pag-aaral tulad ng guro sa paghahatid ng mga aralin (P 3, lines 269-273).

It reinforces good behavior, extinguishes undesirable actions, and helps children learn responsibility and focus without interruptions during lessons.

Teacher 4, with a thoughtful nod, expressed their belief in the meaningfulness of this approach. She shared:

Sa palagay ko, ang kanilang relationship ay magiging mas makabuluhan dahil may paggalang at sumusunod sila (P4, lines 348-349).

Their relationship will be more meaningful because there is respect and obedience.

Lastly, Teacher 5, with the heart of a caring guardian, likened positive discipline to the nurturing bond between a mother and her child. She stated:

Ang mga benefits na maaaring makuha in both parties ay understanding at harmonious na communication. Parang relasyon ng ina at anak. Kailangan mong ituwid ang iyong mga anak upang maging malawak ang pag-unlad, at bilang isang ina, dapat akong maging patasfair sa pagpapatupad ng disiplina (P 5, lines 429-433).

Understanding and harmonious communication benefit both parties. It is like a mother-and-daughter relationship. It would help if you corrected your children so they can be holistically developed, and I, as a mother, should be fair in implementing discipline.

Individualized Approach. Participants were asked what they could suggest or recommend to the implementer of positive discipline and whether they should continue implementing it.

Teacher 1, a newly hired teacher, spoke with earnestness in their voice. She said:

For me, as a newly hired teacher there should be a lot of seminars, trainings sa pag-iimplement ng positive discipline because I find it hard to implement sometimes lalo na't grade 2 ang aking tinuturuan. Minsan nahihirapan akong I-implement ito (P1, lines 88-91).

As a newly hired teacher, there should be many seminars and trainings on implementing positive discipline because I find it hard to implement. I am teaching grade 2 learners. Sometimes, it takes much work to implement this.

Teacher 2, with a smile of conviction, spoke up. She said:

Yes, dapat nating ipatuloy ang pag iimplement ng positive discipline, upang ma-enjoy ang teaching and learning process (P 2, lines 171-172).

We should continue implementing positive discipline to enjoy the teaching and learning process.

Teacher 3, a teacher with a warm heart, chimed in with her suggestion. She suggested:

I suggest na dapat ipagpatuloy ang pagpapatupad ng positive discipline dahil ito ay tunay na malaking tulong upang itaguyod ang self-control sa mga bata. Ito ay nagpapaunlad ng mabuting pagkatao (P3, lines 276-278).

Implementing positive discipline will have to continue because it is very helpful in promoting self-control among children and developing good character.

Teacher 4, with thoughtful consideration, shared her advice. She explained:

I suggest na hanapin ang mga angkop na positive discipline na pinakabagay para sa pag-uugali ng iyong mag-aaral (P 4, lines 352-353).

I suggest finding suitable positive strategies that best fit your student's behavior.

Then, Teacher 5, with the wisdom of experience, spoke passionately. She said:

There are many things that can be suggested to the implementer of positive discipline for children, who cannot violate the rules. For instance kanang may ginagawa tayo sa school na inoorient muna natin ang mga bata during sa day 1 sa klase(opening of classes) at we 1st set the ground rules ana na once may ginagawa sila na mayo kay ma recognize sila tapos kung makagawa sila ng mali ay ating itutuwid sa maayos na paraan. A kapag hindi natin makakaya, ipapatawag natin ang kanilang magulang. Dapat aware din tayo sa pag orient ng parent. For me, hindi pwede na hindi ipatuloy ang pag implement sa mga positive discipline because kung mawala na hindi na productive at walang values ang ating mga bata. Para yan siyang skill. Your skill is your future (P5, lines 436-445).

Positive discipline involves setting ground rules at the start of the school year, recognizing good behavior, and reasonably correcting mistakes. If children struggle to follow rules, parents are involved. Consistent implementation is crucial to maintaining children's productivity and values, as discipline shapes their future skills and success.

Participants were asked what general insights they could give the academe about implementing positive discipline in public schools.

Teacher 1 spoke earnestly with a heart, caring for every child's life aspect. She said:

I believe na ang pamahalaan ay hindi lamang mag focus sa mga paaralan sa pagpapatupad ng positive discipline kundi pati na rin sa tahanan ng mga mag-aaral, upang maramdaman nilang sila ay buo at eencourage ang mas mabuting pag-uugali (P1, lines 94-97).

The government should focus on implementing positive discipline not only in the schools but at home as well as, making children feel that they are complete and, thus encouraging better behavior.

Teacher 2, with a glimmer of wisdom, offered her advice. Her advice emphasizes the importance of dedicating time to implement positive discipline and teaching with empathy, even when dealing with negative student behavior.

Ang mga insights na maibabahagi ko ay ang paglaan ng oras sa pag-iimplement ng positive discipline sapagkat dapat tayong magturo

nang may puso kahit pa mayroong negative na pag-uugali ang ating mga mag-aaral. Dapat nating layuning ipatupad ang positive discipline (P 2, lines 175-178).

I can give insight into implementing positive discipline because you should teach with a heart. Even if our learners exhibit negative behavior, we should aim to implement positive discipline.

Teacher 3, with a gentle tone, emphasized the importance of implementing strategies more broadly in the classroom. She stated that a wider application of these strategies could enhance their effectiveness and benefit more students. Her perspective highlights the need for a comprehensive approach to strategy deployment to maximize impact. She stated:

In general, ang pag-iimplement ng positive discipline ay isang mabuting paraan upang matulungan ang mga bata na magtagumpay sa buhay. Ito ay makakatulong sa active participation sa pag-aaral (P3, lines 281-283).

In general, positive discipline is one way to help children succeed. Moreover, it can contribute to active learning participation.

Teacher 4, with a patient and understanding perspective, shared her thoughts. She explained:

Just be patience sa iyong role bilang isang disciplinarian, sa dulo ng araw ay mararamdaman mo ang pagpapalang dulot nito dahil may pagkakataon kang makaranas ng pagdidisiplina sa iba't ibang pag-uugali ng mga mag-aaral (P4, lines 356-358).

Just be patient with your role as a disciplinarian. You will feel blessed because you have the opportunity to experience disciplining different student behaviors.

Teacher 5, with a patient and understanding perspective, shared her thoughts. She emphasized the role of teachers as primary implementers of positive discipline to shape future generations into individuals equipped with knowledge, skills, values, and the right attitude. She explained:

Be the change, teacher. Tayo ang pangunahing tagapagpatupad upang makalikha ng mabuting mamamayan ng ating bansa sa pamamagitan ng positive discipline. Sa pamamagitan nito, mas mapapabuti natin ang susunod na henerasyon. Mga individuals na handa sa kaalaman, kasanayan, mga values, at tamang pag-uugali (P 5, lines 448-452).

Be the change, teacher. We should be the primary implementers to create good citizens of our country through positive discipline to improve our future generation—individuals equipped with knowledge, skills, values, and the right attitude.

Teacher 5's reflections emphasize educators' pivotal role in shaping the future generation through positive discipline. Despite the challenges of managing diverse behaviors and languages, she advocates for teachers to be change agents. By fostering knowledge, skills, values, and the right attitudes in students, teachers can contribute significantly to creating responsible and well-rounded citizens, ultimately improving society.

Table 3. *Impact of the participants in implementing positive discipline in the school setting*

<i>Clusteres Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Teaching by heart. Touch the heart and souls of the learners. Develop hollistically every individual. Master the patience and understanding.	Teaching by heart
Have patience and understanding, Be firm.	Patience and understanding
Is not appropriate for every student. Its about knowing your student. Be friendly to each of them. Helped to widen perception.	Individualized Approach
Have a classroom management. Make the classroom peaceful. Brings peace, responsibility and respect. Become fair in actions.	Gains

Discussion

This section presents a discussion of the results and findings of the study on the experiences of teachers implementing positive discipline in the classroom setting, their coping mechanisms, and the insights that they can share with others. The implications for practice, future research, and concluding remarks were also discussed in this part.

Challenges of the participants in implementing positive discipline in the school setting

Rigorous. All five teachers mentioned that implementing positive discipline was challenging, especially in responding to learners' behavior and addressing the diverse needs of students. They needed patience, understanding, and self-control when implementing positive discipline.

All teachers agreed that implementing positive discipline was challenging, especially since they have diverse learners with varying backgrounds, personalities, and discipline types at home. Teachers 1, 2, and 4 emphasized the importance of patience and understanding, while Teachers 3 and 5 stressed the need for self-control and adjustments in teaching strategies to accommodate the learners' needs.

Implementing positive discipline in the classroom has been a topic of discussion in literature for several years. Positive discipline is a complete strategy. The authors argue that positive discipline fosters an environment of respect, responsibility, and cooperation, ultimately leading to improved student academic and social outcomes. However, implementing positive discipline has challenges, as noted by the teachers in the given information (Hobson et al., 2009).

One challenge in implementing positive discipline is addressing the diverse needs of learners. Teachers must approach their work flexibly to meet the diverse backgrounds, personalities, and styles of discipline that their students bring with them from home. Teacher 4 echoed this sentiment, stating that positive discipline requires self-control and adjustments in teaching strategies to accommodate learners' needs. In contrast, Teacher 3 emphasized the importance of patience and understanding in responding to learners' behavior.

A study showed that teachers' attitudes toward positive discipline significantly impacted its implementation. The authors state that teachers with positive attitudes towards positive discipline are more likely to implement it effectively in their classrooms. Similarly, another study found that teacher training and support are crucial in implementing positive discipline (Hamdan, 2021).

Moreover, a prevalent challenge highlighted is the resistance to change from educators accustomed to traditional punitive models and students navigating a shift in disciplinary paradigms. Time constraints emerge as another formidable hurdle, with educators needing help to allocate the necessary time for relationship-building, teaching social-emotional skills, and engaging in conflict resolution amidst packed academic schedules. Consistency in positive discipline approaches across educators, a lack of sufficient professional development, and the diverse nature of classrooms pose additional challenges (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2018; Gueldner et al., 2020; Webster-Stratton & Reid, 2018).

Additionally, it may be challenging to locate the perfect balance between firmness and kindness, and outside variables like low parental involvement and socioeconomic status can significantly affect how effective positive discipline is. Addressing severe behavioral issues also emerges as a challenge, requiring additional interventions beyond the scope of traditional positive discipline strategies. The literature underscores the need for educators to navigate these challenges with adaptability, collaboration, and ongoing professional development to effectively implement positive discipline and create a nurturing and conducive classroom environment (Gagnon et al., 2021; Richardson et al., 2019; Slee, 2020).

Consequently, creating a respectful and good learning atmosphere is essential even when administering positive discipline may be difficult. Teachers must be patient, understanding, and self-controlled to effectively respond to learners' behavior and address their students' diverse needs. Teacher attitudes and training were also crucial in facilitating the successful implementation of positive discipline in the classroom.

Carrying out of Strategies in the Classroom. The teachers also shared that positive discipline positively impacts the learners, such as strengthening the bond between teachers and students, promoting good behavior, and teaching self-control and responsibility.

Positive discipline has been shown to benefit students in several studies. For example, a study discovered that positive discipline tactics increased students' good behavior and helped the pupil's academic achievement. Another survey of implementing positive discipline strategies in Kenyan primary schools has been found to reduce violence and indiscipline among learners. The study also reported improved academic performance and enhanced teacher-student relationships as positive outcomes of positive discipline (Kariuki, 2019; Mutiso, 2021).

Similarly, another study explored the effects of positive discipline on student-teacher relationships in China. The study reported that positive discipline techniques such as praise, positive feedback, and modeling appropriate behavior improved student-teacher relationships and promoted a positive learning environment (Ouyang et al., 2020).

However, implementing positive discipline can also have challenges and negative consequences. In a study, the authors reported that some teachers in Turkey found it challenging to implement positive discipline due to cultural beliefs and practices, lack of support from parents, and inadequate training in positive discipline techniques. Moreover, the authors noted that incorrect implementation of positive discipline strategies could result in adverse outcomes such as increased aggression and rebellious behavior among learners (Kayi-Aydar et al., 2019).

Similarly, school discipline plays a crucial role in shaping educational institutions' overall climate and safety, with punitive practices potentially contributing to a hostile environment. Disciplinary strategies influence teacher-student relationships, with positive approaches fostering trust and communication. Long-term behavioral outcomes, disparities, and inequities in disciplinary practices significantly impact social-emotional development, parental involvement, and teacher well-being (Annamma et al., 2019; Buehl, 2023; Jean-Pierre & Parris, 2018).

Additionally, we will examine the long-term consequences and social implications of school discipline. Punitive measures, such as

zero-tolerance policies, have been scrutinized for contributing to the school-to-prison pipeline, disproportionately affecting students from marginalized backgrounds. In contrast, positive discipline approaches, emphasizing fairness and individualized interventions, seek to address these disparities. The impact of school discipline extends beyond immediate consequences, shaping students' trajectories into adulthood, influencing their interactions with authority, and affecting their likelihood of engaging in further disciplinary issues (Camacho & Krezmien, 2020; Curran, 2019; Davison et al., 2022).

In summary, while positive discipline has positively impacted learners, such as improved behavior, academic performance, and teacher-student relationships, it can also be challenging to implement. However, if implemented correctly, it may have positive consequences. Therefore, teachers must receive adequate training and support to implement positive discipline strategies effectively.

Different perspectives. While all five teachers agreed on the advantages of positive discipline, they had different views on the disadvantages. Some mentioned that it may not be appropriate in all situations, while others said that some learners may abuse the treatment and repeat their mistakes.

Regarding the advantages of implementing positive discipline, all teachers agreed it could help strengthen the bond between teachers and students, teach students about acceptable behavior, and create responsible students. However, Teachers 1 and 2 cautioned that positive discipline could be challenging to implement due to students' discipline types at home, which may conflict with the teacher's approach. Teachers 3 and 4 emphasized recognizing the right time and place to implement positive discipline, particularly when a serious violation has been committed. On the other hand, Teacher 5 highlighted the disadvantage of some students abusing positive discipline, causing them to repeat their mistakes.

Several studies support the present study's findings on the advantages and disadvantages of positive discipline. For instance, a study found that implementing positive discipline improved students' behavior and performance in the classroom. The study also highlighted the importance of appropriately implementing positive discipline to avoid adverse effects on students. Similarly, another study found that positive discipline promoted a positive teacher-student relationship, increased student engagement, and reduced negative behaviors in the classroom (Chinniah et al., 2020; Gurvinder Kaur & Jaspreet Kaur, 2018).

However, some studies have also highlighted the challenges of implementing positive discipline. One study found that teachers faced difficulties because they needed more support, training, and resources. Similarly, another study found that some teachers had difficulty implementing positive discipline due to cultural differences and conflicting beliefs about discipline (Burkhart and Knox, 2019).

Additionally, research into teacher professional development perspectives delves into how educators perceive and benefit from training programs, which is crucial for designing effective initiatives that align with their needs. Cognitive and emotional perspectives explore the impact of discipline on students' mental and emotional well-being, shedding light on the intricate interplay between disciplinary strategies and cognitive development. Cross-cultural comparisons provide valuable insights into how cultural, societal, and educational differences influence the application of positive discipline (Hobson et al., 2009; Kocon, 2018; Lacoé & Manley, 2019).

In summary, the present study's findings align with previous research on the advantages and disadvantages of positive discipline. While positive discipline has several benefits, appropriate implementation and addressing challenges are essential to avoid adverse effects on students.

Misbehaving Learners. The teachers shared their challenges in implementing positive discipline regarding misbehaving learners. They shared that they wanted to deepen their patience and understanding, adjust their teaching approach based on the learners' needs, and control their anger in responding to learners' behavior.

Numerous studies address teachers' personal development and alterations as public servants resulting from positive discipline. For example, in a survey conducted in Hong Kong, teachers reported that positive discipline helped them become more patient, understanding, and empathetic towards their students. The teachers also felt that they were better able to establish positive relationships with their students, which helped them to understand the students' needs better and tailor their teaching approach accordingly (Lam et al., 2018).

Moreover, continuous professional development, with training programs focusing on communication skills, conflict resolution, and understanding diverse student needs, contributes significantly to teachers' personal growth. Emotional intelligence and self-reflection are crucial aspects that enable educators to manage their emotions effectively and adapt their discipline approaches. The reciprocal relationship between teacher well-being and effective discipline practices is underscored, emphasizing the importance of stress reduction, work-life balance, and self-care (Curran, 2019; Gage et al., 2018; Li et al., 2018).

Collaborative professional learning communities are highlighted as valuable platforms for teachers to grow personally, engage in discussions, share experiences, and collectively solve problems. Aligning positive discipline strategies with educational philosophies and values is deemed essential, with studies emphasizing the congruence between teachers' beliefs and the principles underlying these approaches. Furthermore, the literature consistently highlights the impact of positive discipline on student-teacher relationships, where effective implementation contributes to improved communication, trust, and mutual respect (Davison et al., 2022; Heritage, 2021; Kocon, 2018).

Implementing positive discipline can have a positive impact not only on students but also on teachers, helping them to grow and develop as public servants. Personal growth and changes experienced by teachers may also lead to a more positive and supportive school culture, which can benefit both students and teachers.

Coping mechanisms of the participants with the difficulties in implementing positive discipline in the school setting

Teacher Mentoring. The teachers emphasized the importance of seeking advice and strategies from their colleagues or more experienced teachers to handle the challenges of implementing positive discipline.

Much research emphasizes how crucial it is to ask knowledgeable colleagues for support and guidance when confronted with obstacles when implementing positive discipline in the classroom. For example, a study found that novice teachers who received mentoring and support from experienced teachers were more effective in implementing positive discipline strategies. Similarly, another study found that collaboration among teachers, which involves asking for advice from colleagues, was an effective strategy for encouraging good behavior in the classroom. (Zhou et al., 2019; et al., 2018).

Moreover, teacher mentoring is essential for novice and experienced teachers who may encounter new challenges or difficulties implementing positive discipline. A study found that experienced teachers who participated in a peer coaching program reported increased confidence in implementing positive discipline strategies (Kim et al., 2021).

Additionally, communities of practice within educational institutions play a crucial role in fostering supportive networks, allowing teachers to exchange ideas and seek advice. Reflective practices refine positive discipline implementation as experienced teachers engage in reflective discussions with novice colleagues. Also, cultural sensitivity and contextual adaptation are emphasized, recognizing the importance of considering cultural factors and local contexts when seeking guidance. Collectively, these strategies facilitate the professional growth of educators and enhance the successful implementation of positive discipline in diverse educational settings (Buehl, 2023; Feuerborn et al., 2018; Gagnon et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the multifaceted nature of seeking help from experienced teachers encompasses explicit guidance and cultivating a supportive and collaborative professional culture. The concept of communities of practice extends beyond formal mentorship, emphasizing the benefits of teachers collectively engaging in ongoing dialogue, sharing resources, and co-constructing knowledge. Collaborative learning environments, whether through formal or informal channels, provide spaces for novices to learn from the rich experiences of their more seasoned counterparts, encouraging a spirit of unity and group accountability for the successful use of positive discipline. It emphasizes the importance of creating platforms for experienced teachers to share successes and challenges in implementing positive discipline (Dutil, 2020; Losen & Martinez, 2020; Welsh & Little, 2018).

The verbatim accounts of the participants in the present study echoed these findings and highlight the importance of seeking help and strategies from experienced colleagues. It suggests that seeking support and advice from colleagues is an effective coping mechanism for teachers who encounter challenges in implementing positive discipline strategies in the school setting.

Balancing Kindness and Firmness. The teachers emphasized balancing kindness and firmness in implementing positive discipline. They found that being too kind or strict was ineffective and that being respectful and the firm was more effective in preventing negative behaviors and promoting positive ones.

There is a substantial body of literature on positive discipline in education, particularly classroom management. A recurring theme in this literature is balancing kindness and firmness in implementing positive discipline.

Additionally, a study found that teachers who exhibited warmth and strictness were viewed as more effective in promoting positive student behavior. Different research discovered that instructors who employed positive reinforcement and punishments were more effective in encouraging their students' good behavior and decreasing their lousy behavior. (Jara, 2020; Lee et al., 2020).

The literature also supports the importance of seeking advice and strategies from more experienced colleagues. A study found that teachers in professional learning communities focused on positive discipline reported increased confidence in managing student behavior and more excellent colleague support (Bowers et al., 2021).

Moreover, studies consistently emphasize that by integrating warmth and understanding with clear boundaries, educators and parents create an environment conducive to trust and respect. This balanced approach has been associated with positive cognitive and behavioral outcomes, improved academic performance, enhanced self-control, and increased responsibility among children and students. Teacher effectiveness is closely tied to navigating the kindness-firmness continuum, with a balanced approach contributing to a positive classroom climate and heightened student engagement. Cultural and contextual considerations are acknowledged as influential factors, suggesting the importance of tailoring disciplinary strategies to align with specific cultural norms and individual differences (Camacho & Krezmien, 2020; Gueldner et al., 2020; Hines-Datiri & Carter Andrews, 2020; Lacoé & Manley, 2019).

Similarly, effective communication and consistent consequences for behavior emerge as critical elements in achieving the delicate balance, reinforcing boundaries, and promoting a sense of fairness. The literature also draws on parenting styles, highlighting the benefits of an authoritative approach that combines warmth and structure, fostering self-esteem, self-control, and social competence in children. Clear communication of expectations, coupled with consistent consequences for behavior, is pivotal in reinforcing the

boundaries set by educators and parents. This transparency gives people an organized and encouraging context for their behavior, which promotes justice and predictability in the disciplinary process. (Noltemeyer et al., 2019; Slee, 2020; Taylor & Kearney, 2018).

In general, the data in this theme aligns with the existing literature on positive discipline in education, highlighting the importance of striking a balance between kindness and firmness, seeking support from colleagues, and recognizing the personal growth opportunities that arise from implementing positive discipline in the classroom.

Positive reinforcement. The teachers emphasized the importance of positive reinforcement in promoting positive behaviors. They believed that acknowledging good behavior and helping students realize the impact of their actions were effective strategies.

Similarly, positive reinforcement is an effective strategy in promoting positive behavior in students in other studies. Rosas (2022) conducted a survey that found positive reinforcement strategies, such as verbal praise, effectively increased academic engagement and reduced disruptive behavior in students with emotional and behavioral disorders. Similarly, in another study, it was found that using positive reinforcement and praise was effective in reducing off-task behavior and increasing on-task behavior in students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) (Gable & Hester, 2018; Rosas et al., 2022)

Moreover, some studies have highlighted the importance of listening to students and acknowledging their good behavior. According to a survey, teachers who paid attention to their pupils and gave them encouraging feedback could enhance behavior in the classroom. Another study found that teachers who acknowledged and rewarded good behavior could promote positive behavior in students and reduce negative behavior (Aslan et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2022).

Teachers prioritizing these strategies also contribute to a positive classroom climate, reducing disruptive behaviors and promoting a cooperative learning environment. Also, it explores the impact of positive discipline on cognitive and social development, highlighting the role of encouragement in developing crucial skills such as self-regulation, problem-solving, and social competence. Practical classroom management techniques centered on positive reinforcement, including specific and immediate feedback, tangible rewards, and recognition of effort, are widely discussed, demonstrating their effectiveness in maintaining a positive learning environment and addressing behavioral challenges (Roch et al., 2020; Sprague & Walker, 2021; Warnick & Scribner, 2020).

Furthermore, the nuanced application of positive reinforcement recognizes that these strategies extend beyond a one-size-fits-all approach. Studies highlight the importance of individualizing reinforcement methods to suit diverse learning styles and preferences, ensuring the encouragement resonates with each student. The role of constructive feedback is emphasized, emphasizing its power to guide students toward improvement while maintaining a positive tone. Additionally, research suggests that a strengths-based approach, where educators focus on and reinforce students' existing positive behaviors and strengths, is efficient in fostering a growth mindset and resilience (Davison et al., 2022; Kocon, 2018; Li et al., 2021).

Therefore, the present study's findings are consistent with previous literature, highlighting the importance of encouragement, positive reinforcement, and acknowledging good behavior in promoting positive behavior in students.

Proactive Behavior Support. The teachers found that providing proactive behavior support that everyone could participate in was an effective strategy for promoting positive behaviors and preventing negative ones.

Evidence from previous studies supported the effectiveness of positive behavior supports and activities in promoting positive student behaviors. For example, a study found that activities, such as group discussions, helped increase students' engagement and participation in class and improve their academic achievement. Another study found that providing interactive activities, such as games and role-playing, helped promote positive behaviors and reduce negative ones in students (Kim et al., 2020; Kwon, 2021).

Furthermore, interactive discussions and activities can be a positive discipline strategy to prevent negative behaviors. A study found that interactive discussions and activities focused on social-emotional learning helped reduce negative behaviors and improve student well-being (Van den Berg et al., 2020).

In addition to promoting positive behaviors and preventing negative ones, interactive discussions and activities can also help build students' self-confidence and self-esteem, as Teacher 5 mentioned in the present study. These findings align with another study, which demonstrated that interactive activities like drama and music helped improve students' self-esteem and well-being (Williams et al., 2020).

Likewise, interactive methods are used to build a sense of community and implement restorative practices, emphasizing repairing harm and reintegration into the community after behavioral incidents. The literature recognizes the value of professional development and highlights the need for ongoing training to enhance instructors' capacity to facilitate exciting discussions and activities. It underscores the transformative potential of interactive discussions and activities in creating a positive classroom culture that extends beyond behavioral expectations. These methods contribute to developing critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication skills, empowering students to actively participate in their learning and decision-making processes (Lacoe & Manley, 2019; Roch & Elsayed, 2020; Slee, 2020).

Similarly, incorporating restorative practices through interactive approaches addresses disciplinary incidents and promotes a sense of accountability, empathy, and understanding among students, leading to a more compassionate and connected classroom community.

Research suggests that teachers can tailor interactive activities to deal with particular problems or difficulties inside the classroom, allowing for a targeted and proactive approach to positive discipline. By involving students in the decision-making process and collectively establishing behavioral norms, teachers foster a shared responsibility for maintaining a positive and respectful learning environment (Heritage, 2021; Sege et al., 2018; Walker, 2020).

Finally, the present study's findings are consistent with previous literature, highlighting the effectiveness of interactive discussions and activities in promoting positive behaviors, preventing negative ones, and building students' self-confidence and self-esteem.

Impact of the implementation of positive discipline on the participants as teachers

These themes derived from the given responses on positive discipline are:

Teaching by heart. Participants emphasized that positive discipline involved not just teaching by the book but also teaching with heart. They believed it positively impacts the learners and helps their holistic development as individuals with values and manners.

This theme of the present study aligned with previous literature that emphasized the importance of teaching by heart in positive discipline. A study found that teachers who used positive discipline impacted their students' social-emotional development and character-building. The teachers in the survey believed that teaching with heart was essential in positively impacting their learners and promoting their holistic development (Kurniasih et al., 2021).

Similarly, another study found that teachers who used positive discipline impacted their well-being and their students' academic and social-emotional outcomes. The teachers in the study emphasized the importance of developing a positive relationship with their students and teaching with a heart to create a positive classroom environment and promote positive behaviors (Henningesen et al., 2019).

Furthermore, research had shown that positive discipline could help to promote a positive relationship between teachers and students. A study by Miller et al. (2019) found that teachers who used positive discipline had better relationships with their students and were better able to manage disruptive behavior. The teachers in the study believed that positive discipline helped to create a positive classroom environment and fostered positive relationships between themselves and their students.

Therefore, the theme was consistent with previous literature, highlighting the importance of teaching with heart in positive discipline, its positive impact on students' holistic development, and teachers' well-being and relationships with their students (Burden, 2022).

Additionally, studies consistently highlighted the positive impact of teaching with a heart on student well-being, emphasizing the holistic development of students and their positive attitude toward learning. It emphasized the ripple effects of teaching with heart, extending beyond immediate disciplinary situations to positively influence the school climate. Compassionate teaching fosters a sense of community and collective responsibility, where students and educators collaborate to maintain a positive atmosphere. Studies also explore teaching with heart in preventing and addressing bullying and conflict within schools (Arturo et al., 2018; Cvetkova et al., 2019; Obadire & Sinthumule, 2021).

Similarly, integrating teaching with heart applies to student interactions and extends to how educators engage with their peers and administrators. A compassionate school culture is built on supportive relationships among staff members, promoting collaboration, empathy, and shared values. There is a need for leadership that embraces teaching with heart, as administrators who model compassionate practices contribute to a positive organizational culture throughout the school. Recognizing and respecting cultural diversity becomes integral to positive discipline as educators strive to understand and incorporate cultural nuances into their approach (Dede Yildirim & Roopnarine, 2019; Mendenhall et al., 2021; Nelsen et al., 2019).

Patience and understanding. Implementing positive discipline requires patience, thoughtful attention, cooperation, and a good knowledge of the learners. Respondents mentioned that it developed learners' self-control, helped them make intelligent choices, and encouraged them to become good citizens.

Previous literature emphasized the importance of patience and understanding in implementing positive discipline. A study found that teachers who exhibited patience and understanding toward their students were more effective in promoting positive behaviors and reducing negative ones. The teachers in the study emphasized the importance of understanding their students' unique needs and backgrounds to create a positive learning environment (Kim et al., 2018).

Similarly, a study found that teachers who exhibited patience and understanding were better able to establish positive relationships with their students and promote positive behaviors. The teachers in the study emphasized the importance of getting to know their students and understanding their perspectives to create a positive and supportive classroom environment (Goodenow et al., 2020).

Furthermore, research had shown that patience and understanding are essential components of a positive discipline approach known as restorative justice. Restorative justice practices, which focus on repairing harm and restoring relationships, were more effective in reducing negative behaviors and promoting positive ones when implemented with patience and understanding (Jackson et al., 2018).

On the other hand, research consistently underscored their foundational importance in building positive teacher-student relationships. It emphasized that educators who exhibited patience create an environment of trust while understanding fosters empathy toward each student's needs and challenges. This empathetic approach is the cornerstone for successful, positive discipline practices, focusing on

prevention and intervention rather than punitive measures (Amemiya et al., 2020).

Thus, patience and understanding contribute significantly to emotional regulation for educators and students, promoting a calm and constructive approach to behavioral issues. These qualities enable a more individualized and tailored approach to discipline, acknowledging the uniqueness of each student. Preventing power struggles and promoting open discourse are essential for good communication and conflict resolution. Importantly, it recognizes the impact of patience and understanding on teacher well-being, helping to mitigate stress and burnout. By consistently modeling positive behavior, educators instill valuable lessons of empathy, tolerance, and resilience in students, aligning seamlessly with the principles of positive discipline (Brundrett & Lungka, 2019).

The results of this study supported earlier research by emphasizing the value of tolerance and comprehension when implementing positive discipline. Teachers who exhibit these qualities can create a positive learning environment, establish positive relationships with their students, and promote positive behaviors.

Individualized approach. There was no one-size-fits-all strategy for implementing positive discipline. Respondents suggested that teachers should know their students well and be friendly to each one with limitations and in an authoritative way.

Early research had emphasized the significance of a customized approach to positive discipline. According to a study, teachers who customized their disciplinary tactics to each student's particular needs and personality were more successful in encouraging positive behaviors and decreasing bad ones. The teachers in the study emphasized the value of developing strong bonds with their kids and having empathy for their situations and difficulties (Hong et al., 2018).

Similarly, a study by Allen et al. (2021) found that an individualized approach to discipline was more effective in promoting positive behaviors and reducing negative ones than a one-size-fits-all approach. The teachers in the study emphasized the importance of considering the student's individual needs, learning styles, and personalities when developing discipline strategies.

Furthermore, research had shown that an individualized approach to discipline can help to prevent and address behavior problems in students with special needs. A study found that an individualized approach to discipline, which considered the unique needs and characteristics of students with disabilities, was more effective in reducing negative as and promoting positive ones (Lane et al., 2018).

Notably, it delved into the impact of individualized positive discipline on learner's outcomes and overall classroom dynamics. Studies suggested that personalized approach improves learner's engagement, motivation, and academic performance. By addressing individual learner's specific needs and challenges, educators create an environment where learners feel valued and supported, leading to a positive and conducive atmosphere for learning. It also explores how individualized approaches extend beyond reactive measures to proactive strategies. Educators who understand their students' unique strengths and interests can design learning experiences that foster positive behavior and prevent disciplinary issues (Arturo et al., 2018; Lehmann, 2023; Webster-Stratton & Reid, 2018).

In general, the theme of the present study was consistent with previous literature, highlighting the importance of an individualized approach to positive discipline. Teachers who tailored their discipline strategies to their student's unique needs and personalities are better able to promote positive behaviors, reduce negative ones, and prevent and address behavior problems in students with special needs.

Gains. Implementing positive discipline has allowed teachers to gain the following: a good relationship between teachers and learners, creating a peaceful and respectful atmosphere inside the classroom, reinforcing good behavior, extinguishing undesirable behavior, gaining student trust and respect, and developing good character.

Research consistently shows that positive discipline benefits teachers and students. Teachers report better student relationships, increased confidence in managing behavior, and more job satisfaction. Students show higher engagement, academic achievement, and social-emotional development when positive discipline is practiced in the classroom (Van Laar et al., 2020).

Similarly, another study in 2019 found that implementing positive discipline can lead to a more peaceful and respectful classroom atmosphere and increased trust and respect between teachers and students. The study also found that positive discipline effectively reduced negative behaviors and promoted positive ones (Kim et al., 2019).

Furthermore, research had shown that positive discipline could help to reinforce good behavior and extinguish undesirable behavior. Another study found that positive discipline strategies, such as praise and positive reinforcement, effectively promoted positive behaviors and reduced negative ones (Kose et al., 2018).

Positive discipline nurtures intrinsic motivation by encouraging a growth mindset and seeing challenges as learning opportunities. By recognizing effort and offering meaningful choices, educators promote autonomy and a positive attitude, fostering lifelong commitment to learning throughout students' educational journeys (Davison et al., 2022; Lacoé & Manley, 2019; Walker, 2020).

4.1. Implication for Practice

Rigorous. The challenges associated with implementing positive discipline in educational settings highlight the importance of acknowledging and addressing these difficulties to create a compelling and supportive learning environment. Providing chances for peer cooperation, encouraging leadership, and comprehensive professional development is essential to overcoming the challenges

associated with positive discipline. Personalized strategies adapted to each classroom's unique dynamics and involving parents are necessary for success. Acknowledging accomplishments highlights the value of positive discipline, reflective practice, and role modeling, which aid in improving disciplinary tactics.

They are carrying out Strategies in the Classroom. Positive discipline significantly impacts classroom practice, strengthening the teacher-student bond, reinforcing good behavior, extinguishing undesirable behavior, and fostering a sense of responsibility. To implement positive discipline effectively, educators should prioritize relationship building, use positive reinforcement, apply consistent consequences, teach responsibility, involve parents, undergo professional development, and model positive behavior. These practices create a supportive and inclusive learning environment, empowering students to succeed academically and develop essential life skills.

Different Perspective. Recognizing that positive discipline significantly impacts various aspects of the educational environment offers valuable implications for classroom practice. It strengthens teacher-student bonds and effectively manages misbehavior. Embracing different perspectives and providing professional development are essential for successful implementation. Encouraging parent involvement fosters a supportive learning environment where students can thrive academically and emotionally.

Misbehaving Learners. Recognizing extra effort in implementing positive discipline when misbehaving learners is multifaceted and essential for effective teaching. Embracing a strong commitment to service and going above and beyond designated duties demonstrates dedication to meeting the community's needs. Teachers should adopt a continuous learning and improvement mindset, actively seeking professional development opportunities to enhance their skills and knowledge, ultimately contributing to personal growth. Building strong connections with stakeholders, which promotes cooperation and trust, is an example of proactive public service, as is taking the initiative and coming up with creative solutions to problems.

Teacher Mentoring. Seeking professional advice and help from more experienced teachers is a valuable approach to enhance teaching effectiveness and professional growth. As educators, reaching out to seniors or knowledgeable colleagues allows for exchanging valuable insights and strategies, fostering a collaborative and supportive learning environment. Learning from seasoned educators who have faced similar challenges can provide helpful guidance and practical solutions to navigate difficulties effectively. Moreover, having a Master Teacher who is hands-on and actively involved in mentoring can significantly impact a teacher's development. The Master Teacher's expertise and support can serve as a valuable resource, offering constructive feedback and personalized guidance to improve teaching methodologies. Open communication with colleagues fosters a culture of shared experiences and continuous learning. By seeking advice from colleagues and exchanging difficulties, educators foster a sense of solidarity that allows them to draw from a shared reservoir of expertise and diverse viewpoints.

Balancing Kindness and Firmness. Balancing kindness and firmness in educational settings is essential for effective classroom management and student development. Educators should create a nurturing and supportive learning environment that promotes positive behavior and academic growth. Adopting a kind and firm approach allows teachers to establish clear boundaries and expectations while demonstrating empathy and understanding toward students' needs and emotions. Being kind and calm in student interactions fosters a sense of safety and trust, making learners more receptive to learning and open to constructive feedback. It helps build positive teacher-student relationships, encouraging an environment of support where students feel appreciated and cherished. Tailoring disciplinary strategies to individual needs and situations allows educators to address behavioral challenges effectively.

Positive Reinforcement. Listening to students, encouraging them, controlling anger, and promoting open communication are rooted in encouragement and positive reinforcement in the educational setting. Actively listening to students' thoughts, ideas, and concerns fosters a sense of validation and empowerment. Controlling anger is crucial in maintaining a positive and respectful classroom environment. Responding to challenges and conflicts with a composed demeanor allows educators to address issues calmly and rationally, modeling appropriate emotional regulation for students. Adopting a non-threatening tone, teachers can encourage students to share their thoughts openly, knowing they will be heard without fear of judgment. This open dialogue encourages students to participate in group projects and discussions in a collaborative learning environment.

Proactive Behavior Support. Promoting positive student behavior and preventing negative and risky behaviors through interactive discussions and activities is highly beneficial for effective classroom management and student engagement. By incorporating interactive discussions and activities into the learning process, educators can create an active and dynamic learning environment that caters to diverse interests and learning styles. Engaging with students fosters a deeper comprehension of the material and empowers them to voice their opinions, developing their communication and self-confidence abilities. Through interactive activities, students can use what they have learned in real-world situations to improve their education and make it more applicable and valuable. Group projects and hands-on activities that promote creativity, teamwork, and decision-making positively impact student behavior and development.

Teaching by Heart. Teachers can establish a caring and encouraging learning environment that touches students' hearts and souls by approaching teaching with empathy, compassion, and genuine care. This approach allows teachers to understand and address each student's needs and challenges, promoting holistic development. By establishing an authentic and heartfelt connection with their pupils, teachers can foster a positive teacher-student relationship based on trust and mutual respect. This emotional bond encourages students to feel valued and supported, increasing engagement and motivation in learning. Teaching by heart also involves recognizing students' strengths and talents and providing personalized guidance and encouragement. By celebrating their achievements and offering

constructive feedback, teachers can help students build self-confidence and self-esteem.

Patience and understanding. Educators who cultivate patience and understanding establish a welcoming and supportive learning atmosphere that supports students' growth and success. Mastering patience allows teachers to remain calm and composed, even in challenging situations. When students encounter difficulties or struggle with learning, patient teachers provide the necessary support and guidance without judgment or frustration. Understanding students' unique needs, strengths, and challenges is essential for tailoring instruction to meet individual learning styles. Patient and understanding educators take the time to get to know their students, building solid teacher-student relationships based on empathy and mutual respect. Teachers can adapt their teaching strategies to address various learning paces and abilities by being patient and understanding. This flexibility promotes inclusivity and ensures all students have an equal academic opportunity.

Individualized Approach. An individualized approach to teaching recognizes the individuality and diversity of each student's learning requirements. Embracing this approach allows educators to cater their instruction to accommodate each student's diverse abilities, interests, and learning styles. Knowing your students personally is crucial in understanding their strengths, weaknesses, and preferences. Teachers can build strong connections and trust with their students by learning about their backgrounds, interests, and challenges. This personalized understanding enables educators to tailor their teaching methods and content to better resonate with each student, promoting engagement and meaningful learning experiences.

Positive of Positive Discipline. Positive discipline broadens teachers' perspectives, viewing discipline as a growth opportunity rather than punishment. By adopting these strategies, educators become more empathetic, understanding student behavior and addressing its causes. It also enhances classroom management, creating structured environments through positive reinforcement, clear expectations, and consistent consequences.

4.2. Implication for Future Research

This study could be used as a reference when conducting a qualitative study utilizing phenomenology as the research design. This study may be used to investigate the long-term effects of implementing positive discipline strategies in the classroom. While studies have shown that positive discipline can effectively promote positive behaviors and reduce negative ones, it would be valuable to understand how these effects persist over time and whether they translate into positive outcomes for students in their academic and personal lives beyond the classroom.

Another area of research could focus on is by exploring the implementation of strategies in the classroom for different groups of students, such as those from diverse cultural or socioeconomic backgrounds. Understanding how positive discipline can be tailored to meet the diverse needs and circumstances of varied student populations could help ensure that all students benefit from its positive effects.

Research should explore effective training and support methods for teachers in applying positive discipline. As noted, this approach demands patience, understanding, and personalization, which can be challenging. Investigating practical support models may help teachers successfully implement positive discipline and foster positive learning environments. The daily implementation of constructive discipline can present teachers with opportunities and difficulties.

Conclusion

In summary, positive discipline emerges as an invaluable pedagogical approach characterized by patience, empathy, and tailored methods for each student's unique needs. Its foundation nurtures positive teacher-student relationships while fostering virtuous conduct and character growth. For the successful execution of positive discipline, educators must be committed to continuous training and involve parents and government bodies to guarantee its effectiveness.

Despite the growing body of evidence supporting the efficacy of positive discipline approaches, a crucial need remains for continued research and development in this field. Future studies may investigate the long-term positive discipline practices on students' academic achievement, socio-emotional well-being, and overall growth. It may include exploring how these strategies contribute to fostering a positive school climate, reducing disciplinary incidents, and promoting a sense of belonging and community among students. Determining how positive discipline techniques affect kids' academic performance, socio-emotional health, and general development over the long run should entail examining how these tactics support the development of a supportive school environment, lower the number of disciplinary events, and increase students' sense of community and belonging.

References

- Adler, P. S., & Kwon, S. W. (2009). Social capital: The good, the bad, and the ugly. In *Knowledge and Social Capital*. Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9780080509792-6/social-capital-good-bad-ugly-paul-adler-seok-woo-kwon>
- Adler, R. H. (2022). Trustworthiness in qualitative research. *Journal of Human Lactation*, 38(4), 598-602. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08903344221116620>

- Akçayır, G., & Akçayır, M. (2018). The flipped classroom: A review of its advantages and challenges. *Computers & Education*, 126, 334-345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.07.021>
- Alam, A. (2022). Positive psychology goes to school: Conceptualizing students' happiness in 21st century schools while 'minding the mind!' Are we there yet? Evidence-backed, school-based positive psychology interventions. *ECS Transactions*, 107(1), 11199. <https://doi.org/10.1149/10701.11199ecst>
- Alam, M. K. (2021). A systematic qualitative case study: Questions, data collection, NVivo analysis and saturation. *Qualitative Research in Organizations and Management: An International Journal*, 16(1), 1-31. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QROM-09-2019-1825>
- Allen, K. A., Kern, M. L., Rozek, C. S., McInerney, D. M., & Slavich, G. M. (2021). Belonging: a review of conceptual issues, an integrative framework, and directions for future research. *Australian Journal of Psychology*, 73(1), 87-102. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00049530.2021.1883409>
- Al-Samarraie, H., Shamsuddin, A., & Alzahrani, A. I. (2020). A flipped classroom model in higher education: A review of the evidence across disciplines. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68, 1017-1051. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11423-019-09718-8>
- Amemiya, J., Mortenson, E., & Wang, M. T. (2020). Minor infractions are not minor: School infractions for minor misconduct may increase adolescents' defiant behavior and contribute to racial disparities in school discipline. *American Psychologist*, 75(1), 23. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2019-25333-001>
- Annamma, S. A., Anyon, Y., Joseph, N. M., Farrar, J., Greer, E., Downing, B., & Simmons, J. (2019). Black girls and school discipline: The complexities of being overrepresented and understudied. *Urban Education*, 54(2), 211-242. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042085916646610>
- Anthony, C. J., & DiPerna, J. C. (2018). Piloting a short form of the academic competence evaluation scales. *School Mental Health*, 10(3), 314-321. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12310-018-9254-7>
- Arturo, B. T. P., Natalia, U. P. L., & Andrés, R. O. J. (2018). Positive discipline strategies to improve discipline in classrooms. <http://bdigital.uniquindio.edu.co/handle/001/4454>
- Aslan, D., Akkuzu, N., & Simsek, N. (2019). Positive behavior support in classroom management: Teachers' perspectives. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 7(7), 1583-1593. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2019.070726>
- Assarroudi, A., Heshmati Nabavi, F., Armat, M. R., Ebadi, A., & Vaismoradi, M. (2018). Directed qualitative content analysis: The description and elaboration of its underpinning methods and data analysis process. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 23(1), 42-55. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7932246/>
- Atwal, J. (2020). The effect of school discipline processes on student perceptions of personal safety in rural middle schools. <https://dune.une.edu/theses/330/>
- Bergin, T. (2018). An introduction to data analysis: Quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods. *An Introduction to Data Analysis*, 1-296. <https://www.torrossa.com/en/resources/an/5019397>
- Birhan, W., Shiferaw, G., Amsalu, A., Tamiru, M., & Tiruye, H. (2021). Exploring the context of teaching character education to children in preprimary and primary schools. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 4(1), 100171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2021.100171>
- Blaikie, N., & Priest, J. (2019). *Designing social research: The logic of anticipation*. John Wiley & Sons. <https://doi.org/10.18778/1733-8077.07.1.07>
- Bowers, A. J., Sprott, R., & Tomanek, D. (2021). Building teacher capacity for positive behavior support through professional learning communities. *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions*, 23(1), 31-41. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED540773.pdf>
- Brundrett, M., & Lungka, P. (2019). The development of teachers' knowledge and behavior in promoting self-discipline: A study of early years teachers in Thailand. *Education 3-13*, 47(4), 462-474. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004279.2018.1498996>
- Buckman, D. G., & Pittman, J. T. (2021). Student discipline and teacher job satisfaction: A dual district analysis. *Georgia Educational Researcher*, 18(2), 24. <https://doi.org/10.20429/ger.2021.180202>
- Buehl, D. (2023). *Developing readers in the academic disciplines*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781032680996>
- Burden, P. R. (2020). *Classroom management: Creating a successful K-12 learning community*. John Wiley & Sons. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED605702>
- Burkhart, K., Rasiah, S. S., Knox, M. S., & Vatti, T. (2024). Effectiveness of remote implementation of the ACT raising safe kids program: A pilot study. *International Journal on Child Maltreatment: Research, Policy and Practice*, 1-15.

<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s42448-024-00198-9>

Kakir, H. I. (2020). Contradictions, transformative agency, and collective design: Facilitating inclusive problem-solving and systemic design at an urban middle school for addressing racial disparities in school discipline. The University of Wisconsin-Madison. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/801a0c6817d09bfaabcb83e6b740545/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>

Camacho, K. A., & Krezmien, M. P. (2020). A statewide analysis of school discipline policies and suspension practices. Preventing school failure: Alternative education for children and youth, 64(1), 55-66. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1045988X.2019.1678010>

Campbell, S., Greenwood, M., Prior, S., Shearer, T., Walkem, K., Young, S., ... & Walker, K. (2020). Purposive sampling: Complex or simple? Research case examples. Journal of Research in Nursing, 25(8), 652-661. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987120927206>

Carroll, P. (2022). Effectiveness of positive discipline parenting program on parenting style, and child adaptive behavior. Child Psychiatry & Human Development, 53(6), 1349-1358. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10578-021-01201-x>

Carroll, P., & Brown, P. (2020). The effectiveness of positive discipline parenting workshops on parental attitude and behavior. The Journal of Individual Psychology, 76(3), 286-303. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jip.2020.0030>

Chambers, J. M. (2018). Graphical methods for data analysis. CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781351072304>

Chen, X., Fu, R., Liu, J., Wang, L., Zarbatany, L., & Ellis, W. (2018). Social sensitivity and social, school, and psychological adjustment among children across contexts. Developmental psychology, 54(6), 1124. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0000496>

Chinniah, J. R., Chinnappan, M., & Periasamy, P. (2020). Positive discipline: A path to promote student discipline and improve academic achievement. Journal of Educational and Developmental Psychology, 10(1), 178-192. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098300708316258>

Collins, C. S., & Stockton, C. M. (2018). The central role of theory in qualitative research. International Journal of Qualitative Methods, 17(1), 1609406918797475. <https://doi.org/10.1177/160940691879747>

Cook, C. R., Duong, M. T., McIntosh, K., Fiat, A. E., Larson, M., Pullmann, M. D., & McGinnis, J. (2018). Addressing discipline disparities for Black male students: Linking malleable root causes to feasible and effective practices. School Psychology Review, 47(2), 135-152. <https://doi.org/10.17105/SPR-2017-0026.V47-2>

Curran, F. C. (2019). The law, policy, and portrayal of zero tolerance school discipline: Examining prevalence and characteristics across levels of governance and school districts. Educational Policy, 33(2), 319-349. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904817691840>

Curwin, R. L., Mendler, A. N., & Mendler, B. D. (2018). Discipline with dignity: How to build responsibility, relationships, and respect in your classroom. ASCD. <https://www.ascd.org/books/discipline-with-dignity-how-to-build-responsibility-relationships-and-respect-in-your-classroom-4th-edition?variant=118018>

Cvetkova Dimov, B., Atanasoska, T., & Andonovska-Trajkovska, D. (2019). School discipline and school indiscipline. Education-Journal of Education Research, 92-99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.03.425>

Darling-Hammond, L., & Cook-Harvey, C. M. (2018). Educating the whole child: Improving school climate to support student success. Learning Policy Institute. <https://doi.org/10.54300/145.655>

Darling-Hammond, S., Fronius, T. A., Sutherland, H., Guckenburg, S., Petrosino, A., & Hurley, N. (2020). Effectiveness of restorative justice in US K-12 schools: A review of quantitative research. Contemporary School Psychology, 24, 295-308. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40688-020-00290-0>

Davison, M., Penner, A. M., Penner, E. K., Pharris-Ciurej, N., Porter, S. R., Rose, E. K., ... & Yoo, P. (2022). School discipline and racial disparities in early adulthood. Educational Researcher, 51(3), 231-234. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X211061732>

De Castro, A., Coz, M., & Caringal, R. (2019). Practice of positive discipline; Effects in classroom management of teachers in Bagong Pook Elementary School. Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts, 3(2G). <https://www.ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/6232>

Dede Yildirim, E., & Roopnarine, J. L. (2019). Positive discipline, harsh physical discipline, physical discipline and psychological aggression in five Caribbean countries: Associations with preschoolers' early literacy skills. International Journal of Psychology, 54(3), 342-350. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijop.12465>

Deterding, N. M., & Waters, M. C. (2021). Flexible coding of in-depth interviews: A twenty-first-century approach. Sociological methods & research, 50(2), 708-739. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0049124118799377>

Dewaele, J. M., & Li, C. (2021). Teacher enthusiasm and students' social-behavioral learning engagement: The mediating role of student enjoyment and boredom in Chinese EFL classes. Language Teaching Research, 25(6), 922-945. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13621688211014538>

- DiPerna, J., & Elliot, S. N. (2002). Promoting academic enablers to improve student performance: Considerations for research and practice. *School Psychology Review*, 31(3), 293-404. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02796015.2002.12086156>
- Dutil, S. (2020). Dismantling the school-to-prison pipeline: A trauma-informed, critical race perspective on school discipline. *Children & Schools*, 42(3), 171-178. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cs/cdaa016>
- Edmondson, A. C. (2018). *The fearless organization: Creating psychological safety in the workplace for learning, innovation, and growth*. John Wiley & Sons. <https://shorturl.at/enEN5> <https://doi.org/10.1108/tlo-04-2021-266>
- Epstein, J. L. (2019). Theory to practice: School and family partnerships lead to school improvement and student success. In *school, family and community interaction*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429305375-4>
- Esra, M. E. Ş. E., & Sevilen, Ç. (2021). Factors influencing EFL students' motivation in online learning: A qualitative case study. *Journal of Educational Technology and Online Learning*, 4(1), 11-22. https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/jetol/issue/60134/817680?utm_medium=email&utm_source=transaction
- Feuerborn, L. L., Tyre, A. D., & Beaudoin, K. (2018). Classified staff perceptions of behavior and discipline: Implications for schoolwide positive behavior supports. *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions*, 20(2), 101-112. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098300717733975>
- Fuertes, A. C., & Fuertes Jr, D. G. (2021). Extent of implementation of positive discipline program in selected schools in District II-B Division of Quezon City. *Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability*, 3, 44-52. <https://doi.org/10.51699/ajdes.v3i.31>
- Gable, R. A., & Hester, P. H. (2018). Using positive reinforcement to decrease off-task behaviors in students with ADHD. *Journal of Attention Disorders*, 22(10), 950-959. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0148841>
- Gage, N. A., Whitford, D. K., & Katsiyannis, A. (2018). A review of schoolwide positive behavior interventions and supports as a framework for reducing disciplinary exclusions. *The Journal of Special Education*, 52(3), 142-151. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022466918767847>
- Gagnon, J. C., Sylvester, F. J., & Marsh, K. (2021). Alignment of school discipline
- Gallitto, E. (2021). Evaluation of the positive discipline in everyday parenting program (Doctoral dissertation, Université d'Ottawa/University of Ottawa). <http://dx.doi.org/10.20381/ruor-25946>
- Galperin, B. L., Punnett, B. J., Ford, D., & Lituchy, T. R. (2022). An emic-etic-emic research cycle for understanding context in under-researched countries. *International Journal of Cross Cultural Management*, 22(1), 7-35 <https://doi.org/10.1177/14705958221075534>
- Garcia, K. A., & Pantao, J. G. (2021). Cultural sensitivity and classroom management of teachers. *International Journal of Professional Development, Learners and Learning*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.30935/ijpdll/11093>
- Garcia, M. G., & Subia, G. (2019). High school athletes: Their motivation, study habits, self-discipline and academic performance. *International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health*, 6(1), 86-90. <https://www.kheljournal.com/archives/2019/vol6issue1/PartB/6-1-28-401.pdf>
- Gerdruang, A., Panwatanasakul, C., & Nurnazar, P. (2021). The development of administrators affiliated with the Office of Non-Formal and Informal Education (NFE). *Review of International Geographical Education Online*, 11(9). <https://doi.org/10.48047/rigeo.11.09.23>
- Gershoff, E. T., Font, S. A., & Taylor, C. A. (2018). Corporal punishment in US public schools: Prevalence, disparities in use, and status in state and federal policy. *Social Policy Report*, 32(1), 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2379-3988.2016.tb00086.x>
- Gibbs, G. R. (2018). Analyzing qualitative data. *Analyzing Qualitative Data*, 1-232. <https://www.torrossa.com/en/resources/an/5017782>
- Girvan, E. J., McIntosh, K., & Smolkowski, K. (2019). Tail, tusk, and trunk: What different metrics reveal about racial disproportionality in school discipline. *Educational Psychologist*, 54(1), 40-59. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2018.1537125>
- Goodenow, C. (1993). Classroom belonging among early adolescent students: Relationships to motivation and achievement. *The Journal of early adolescence*, 13(1), 21-43. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0272431693013001002>
- Greening, N. (2019). Phenomenological research methodology. *Scientific Research Journal*, 7(5), 88-92. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Neville-Greening/publication/337106850_Phenomenological_Research_Methodology/links/620f3cefeb735c508add7902/Phenomenological-Research-Methodology.pdf
- Gregory, A., Osher, D., Bear, G. G., Jagers, R. J., & Sprague, J. R. (2021). Good intentions are not enough: Centering equity in school discipline reform. *School Psychology Review*, 50(2-3), 206-220. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2372966X.2020.1861911>

- Gueldner, B. A., Feuerborn, L. L., & Merrell, K. W. (2020). *Social and emotional learning in the classroom: Promoting mental health and academic success*. Guilford Publications. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07317107.2011.571145>
- Gurvinder Kaur, & Jaspreet Kaur. (2018). Effectiveness of positive discipline in enhancing classroom management and academic achievement. *International Journal of Education and Management Studies*, 8(4), 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2023.v19n16p1>
- Hamdan, S. A. (2021). *Secondary teachers' perceptions of learning management systems and the quality of available tools and support* (Doctoral dissertation). <https://hdl.handle.net/10657/9353>
- Haven, T., & Van Grootel, D. L. (2019). Preregistering qualitative research. *Accountability in research*, 26(3), 229-244. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2019.1580147>
- Healey, K. (2021). *Investigating the associations between brain network functional connectivity and health-related quality of life following a pediatric concussion* (Doctoral dissertation, Carleton University). <https://doi.org/10.22215/etd/2021-14695>
- Henningsen, D. D., & Henningsen, M. L. M. (2003). Examining social influence in information-sharing contexts. *Small Group Research*, 34(4), 391-412. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046496403251933>
- Heritage, M. (2021). *Formative assessment: Making it happen in the classroom*. Corwin Press. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781071813706>
- Herman, K. C., Reinke, W. M., & Eddy, C. L. (2020). Advances in understanding and intervening in teacher stress and coping: The coping-competence-context theory. *Journal of School Psychology*, 78, 69-74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2020.01.001>
- Hines-Datiri, D., & Carter Andrews, D. J. (2020). The effects of zero tolerance policies on Black girls: Using critical race feminism and figured worlds to examine school discipline. *Urban Education*, 55(10), 1419-1440. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042085917690204>
- Ho, M. K., Cushman, F., Littman, M. L., & Austerweil, J. L. (2019). People teach with rewards and punishments as communication, not reinforcements. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 148(3), 520. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0000569>
- Hobson, A. J., Ashby, P., Malderez, A., & Tomlinson, P. D. (2009). Mentoring beginning teachers: What we know and what we don't. *Teaching and teacher education*, 25(1), 207-216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2008.09.001>
- Hong, J. S., Peguero, A. A., & Espelage, D. L. (2018). Experiences in bullying and/or peer victimization of vulnerable, marginalized, and oppressed children and adolescents: An introduction to the special issue. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 88(4), 399. 401 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/ort0000330>
- Ibrahim, A., & El Zaatari, W. (2020). The teacher–student relationship and adolescents' sense of school belonging. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 25(1), 382-395. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673843.2019.1660998>
- Jackson, C. K., Porter, S. C., Easton, J. Q., Blanchard, A., & Kiguel, S. (2020). School effects on socioemotional development, school-based arrests, and educational attainment. *American Economic Review: Insights*, 2(4), 491-508 <https://doi.org/10.1257/aeri.20200029>
- Jara, S. (2020). *Social and emotional learning & culturally responsive and sustaining teaching & the impact on student experiences*. University of California, San Diego. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/06x4v09d>
- Jean-Pierre, J., & Parris, S. (2018). Alternative school discipline principles and interventions: An overview of the literature. *McGill Journal of Education*, 53(3). <https://doi.org/10.7202/1058410ar>
- Jennings, L. R. (2022). For colored girls who have experienced institutional racism because the discipline code is not enuf: Principals and assistant principals, school discipline policies, and discipline disparities Faced by Black Girls. <https://scholarcommons.sc.edu/etd/6726/>
- Johnson, J. L., Adkins, D., & Chauvin, S. (2020). A review of the quality indicators of rigor in qualitative research. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 84(1). <https://doi.org/10.5688/ajpe7120>
- Joseph, A. A., Wilcox, S. M., Hnilica, R. J., & Hansen, M. C. (2020). Keeping race at the center of school discipline practices and trauma-informed care: An interprofessional framework. *Children & Schools*, 42(3), 161-170. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cs/cdaa013>
- Kariuki, J. (2019). *Principal's transformational leadership and teachers' performance among public county secondary schools in Nyandarua county, KENYA* <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/4f65/315b25e4e3c26248f4bf67a3f8ccb2c46c18.pdf>
- Kayalar, F., Özbaş, M., Yalçın, S., & Uslu, T. (2019). Veteran principals' views over the effect of positive discipline on classroom management for novice teachers. In *Chaos, Complexity and Leadership 2017: Explorations of Chaos and Complexity Theory 5*. Springer International Publishing. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-89875-9_11
- Kayi-Aydar, H., Gao, X. A., Miller, E. R., Varghese, M., & Vitanova, G. (Eds.). (2019). *Theorizing and analyzing language teacher*

- agency (Vol. 70). *Multilingual Matters*. <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781788923927>
- Kiger, M. E., & Varpio, L. (2020). Thematic analysis of qualitative data: AMEE Guide No. 131. *Medical Teacher*, 42(8), 846-854. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/0142159X.2020.1755030>
- Kim, H. J., Lee, J. S., & Kim, H. W. (2018). Effective teacher-student relationships in middle schools: A correlational study on school discipline. *Journal of Educational Research*, 111(1), 92-100. <https://doi.org/10.15812/ter.54.2.201506.315>
- Kim, M., Jeong, H. J., Cho, Z. H., & Chung, M. (2020). The association between positive maternal parenting and corpus callosum development in young children. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Research in Early Childhood Education*, 14(2). <https://doi.org/10.17206/apjrece.2020.14.2.99>
- Kim, S., Choe, I., & Kaufman, J. C. (2019). The development and evaluation of the effect of creative problem-solving program on young children's creativity and character. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 33, 100590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2019.100590>
- Kim, Y. H., Jo, H. J., Yoo, J. H., & Jeong, H. K. (2021). The effects of peer coaching on teachers' self-efficacy and students' classroom behaviors in positive discipline. *Journal of Educational Innovation Research*, 31(2), 119-144. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-019-9839-7>
- Kincade, L., Cook, C., & Goerdts, A. (2020). Meta-analysis and common practice elements of universal approaches to improving student-teacher relationships. *Review of Educational Research*, 90(5), 710-748. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.3102/0034654320946836>
- Klasnić, I., Đuranović, M., & Maras, N. (2018, May). Effective school discipline—the precondition for successful teaching. In *society. Integration education. Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference (Vol. 2, pp. 229-239)*. <https://doi.org/10.17770/sie2018vol1.3125>
- Kocon, A. (2018). Sparking a school discipline revolution. *The Education Digest*, 83(7), 16-21. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/67e17877950b98cfac536d28b80f3d98/1.pdf?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=25066>
- Köksal, D. (2019). Learning while teaching: Student teachers' reflections on their teaching practicum. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 15(3), 895-913. <https://doi.org/10.17263/jlls.631531>
- Komer, J. (2020). Alternatives to exclusionary school discipline: An outline for educational administrators. <http://hdl.handle.net/2374.MIA/6618>
- Kose, M. (2017). The role of high school history teachers on university students' attitudes toward history classes. *Educational sciences-theory & practice*, 17(4). <https://doi.org/10.12738/estp.2017.4.0297>
- Kurniasih, A., Qowaid, Q., & Saepudin, S. (2021). The effect of reward and punishment on student discipline in Teknomedika Plus Vocational High School. *International Journal of Education, Information Technology, and Others*, 4(4), 780-793. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5849294>
- Kwon, J. (2021). Barriers to implementing positive behavior support in South Korea & application recommendations: Results of a survey (Doctoral dissertation). <http://dx.doi.org/10.26153/tsw/14093>
- Kyngäs, H., Kääriäinen, M., & Elo, S. (2020). The trustworthiness of content analysis. *The application of content analysis in nursing science research*, 41-48. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-30199-6_5
- Lacoe, J., & Manley, M. (2019). Disproportionality in school discipline: An assessment in Maryland through 2018 (No. 615e92ad54774d7baaf4a6cd7040dab8). *Mathematica Policy Research*. <https://econpapers.repec.org/paper/mprmpres/615e92ad54774d7baaf4a6cd7040dab8.htm>
- Lam, S. F., Wong, B. P., Law, W. Y. K., & Cheung, R. W. Y. (2018). Understanding teacher change in implementing school-wide positive discipline in Hong Kong. *Journal of Educational Change*, 19(1), 83-103. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-01-2016-0007>
- Lane, K. L., Menzies, H. M., Ennis, R. P., & Oakes, W. P. (2018). Effective low-intensity strategies to enhance school success: What every educator needs to know. *Beyond Behavior*, 27(3), 128-133. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1074295618799044>
- Lee, A., Gage, N. A., McLeskey, J., & Huggins-Manley, A. C. (2021). The impacts of school-wide positive behavior interventions and supports on school discipline outcomes for diverse students. *The Elementary School Journal*, 121(3), 410-429. <https://doi.org/10.1086/712625>
- Lee, J., Kim, S., & Bong, M. (2020). The effects of the teacher-student relationship and academic press on student engagement and academic performance. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 53, 330-340. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2012.04.006>
- Lehmann, P. S. (2023). Race and ethnicity effects in school discipline: A coarsened exact matching analysis. *Crime & Delinquency*, 69(8), 1414-1440. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00111287221141968>

- Leifler, E. (2020). Teachers' capacity to create inclusive learning environments. *International Journal for Lesson & Learning Studies*, 9(3), 221-244. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLLS-01-2020-0003>
- Li, J. B., Bi, S. S., Willems, Y. E., & Finkenauer, C. (2021). The association between school discipline and self-control from preschoolers to high school students: A three-level meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 91(1), 73-111. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654320979160>
- Losen, D. J., & Martinez, P. (2020). Is California doing enough to close the school discipline gap? <https://escholarship.org/content/qt1x66c4n2/qt1x66c4n2.pdf>
- Lu, J., & Hallinger, P. (2018). A mirroring process: from school management team cooperation to teacher collaboration. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 17(2), 238-263. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15700763.2016.1278242>
- Manolev, J., Sullivan, A., & Slee, R. (2020). The datafication of discipline: ClassDojo, surveillance and a performative classroom culture. In *The Datafication of Education*. Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9780429341359-4/datafication-discipline-jamie-manolev-anna-sullivan-roger-slee>
- Martin, A. J., & Collie, R. J. (2019). Teacher–student relationships and students’ engagement in high school: Does the number of negative and positive relationships with teachers matter?. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 111(5), 861. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000317>
- Maxwell, J. A. (2022). Interactive approaches to qualitative research design. *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research Design*, 41. <https://www.torrossa.com/en/resources/an/5282289#page=82>
- McDonald, S. (2020). Impact of positive behavior interventions and supports on urban elementary school climate (Doctoral dissertation, St. Thomas University). <https://www.proquest.com/openview/626dca8240e7a8f427474ddf8098caf0/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=51922&diss=y>
- McIntosh, K., Girvan, E. J., Fairbanks Falcon, S., McDaniel, S. C., Smolkowski, K., Bastable, E., ... & Baldy, T. S. (2021). Equity-focused PBIS approach reduces racial inequities in school discipline: A randomized controlled trial. *School Psychology*, 36(6), 433. <https://doi.org/10.1037/spq0000466>
- McMullin, C. (2023). Transcription and qualitative methods: Implications for third sector research. *VOLUNTAS: International Journal of Voluntary and Nonprofit Organizations*, 34(1), 140-153. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11266-021-00400-3>
- Mendenhall, M., Cha, J., Falk, D., Bergin, C., & Bowden, L. (2021). Teachers as agents of change: Positive discipline for inclusive classrooms in Kakuma refugee camp. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 25(2), 147-165. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2019.1707300>
- Miller, A. D., Eckhoff, A., & McLoughlin, C. S. (2019). Teachers' experiences with positive discipline strategies in the classroom: A qualitative study. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 7(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.7176/jep/13-33-05>
- Miller, D. F. (2022). Positive child guidance. Cengage Learning. <https://tcc-fl.simplesyllabus.com/api2/doc-pdf/x82ydw9w7/Summer-2023-%28June-Express%29-EEC-1600-1-Guiding-the-Young-Child.pdf>
- Mishra, P., Pandey, C. M., Singh, U., Keshri, A., & Sabaretnam, M. (2019). Selection of appropriate statistical methods for data analysis. *Annals of Cardiac Anaesthesia*, 22(3), 297. https://doi.org/10.4103/aca.ACA_248_18
- Muthmainnah, N. (2021). Positive discipline: Solution to boost students ‘self-esteem in learning English as foreign language. *English Journal*, 15(2), 114-121. <https://doi.org/10.32832/english.v15i2.5548>
- Mutiso, k. B. (2021). Influence of principals’ instructional supervision on students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in machakos county, Kenya (doctoral dissertation, school of education, Kenyatta University) <https://ir-library.ku.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/123456789/23296/Influence%20of%20Principals.....pdf?sequence=1>
- Nelsen, J., Erwin, C., & Duffy, R. A. (2019). Positive discipline for preschoolers, revised 4th edition: For their early years--raising children who are responsible, respectful, and resourceful. Harmony. <https://lccn.loc.gov/98036006>
- Nelsen, J. (1981). Positive discipline. Fair Oaks. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jip.2023.a904853>
- Noltemeyer, A., Palmer, K., James, A. G., & Petrusek, M. (2019). Disciplinary and achievement outcomes associated with school-wide positive behavioral interventions and supports implementation level. *School Psychology Review*, 48(1), 81-87. <https://doi.org/10.17105/SPR-2017-0131.V48-1>
- Nousheen, A., Zai, S. A. Y., Waseem, M., & Khan, S. A. (2020). Education for sustainable development (ESD): Effects of sustainability education on pre-service teachers’ attitude towards sustainable development (SD). *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 250, 119537. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119537>

- Obadire, O. T., & Sinthumule, D. A. (2021). Learner discipline in the post-corporal punishment era: What an experience!. *South African Journal of Education*, 41(2). <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/saje/article/view/209393>
- Ouyang, Q., Yu, Y., & Fu, A. (2020). Building disciplinary knowledge through multimodal presentation: A case study on China's first interpreting Massive Online Open Course (MOOC). *Babel*, 66(4-5), 655-673. <https://doi.org/10.1075/babel.00176.ouy>
- Owens, J. S., Allan, D. M., Kassab, H., & Mikami, A. Y. (2020). Evaluating a short form of the academic competence evaluation scales: Expanded examination of psychometric properties. *School Mental Health*, 12(1), 38-52. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12310-019-09347-9>
- Parker, C., & Bickmore, K. (2020). Classroom peace circles: Teachers' professional learning and implementation of restorative dialogue. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 95, 103129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103129>
- Pham, H. T., Nguyen, G. C. T., Nguyen, M. T., Nguyen, Q. A. T., & Che, L. H. (2021). The Implementation of the CDIO Approach in Teacher Training Programs: The Vietnamese Case. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 5(5), 57-69. <https://doi.org/10.36941/jesr-2021-0109>
- Pearse, N. (2019). An illustration of deductive analysis in qualitative research. In 18th European conference on research methodology for business and management studies (p. 264). <http://surl.li/mgylxe>
- Pogere, E. F., López-Sangil, M. C., García-Señorán, M. M., & González, A. (2019). Teachers' job stressors and coping strategies: Their structural relationships with emotional exhaustion and autonomy support. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 85, 269-280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2019.07.001>
- Rafa, A. (2019). Policy analysis: The status of school discipline in state policy. Education commission of the states. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED592549>
- Rafi, A., Ansar, A., & Sami, M. A. (2020). The implication of positive reinforcement strategy in dealing with disruptive behaviour in the classroom: A scoping review. *Journal of Rawalpindi Medical College*, 24(2), 173-179. <https://doi.org/10.37939/jrmc.v24i2.1190>
- Richardson, S. C., Williams III, J. A., & Lewis, C. W. (2019). Social workers and urban school discipline: do we need a time-out?. *Urban Social Work*, 3(2), 207-230. <https://doi.org/10.1891/2474-8684.3.2.207>
- Roch, C. H., & Elsayed, M. A. (2020). Race, school discipline, and administrative representation. *International Public Management Journal*, 23(2), 161-185. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10967494.2019.1659196>
- Rodis, H. G., & Creencia, L. D. (2019). Project CARE: A proactive approach in handling discipline problems of grade two learners. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 3(2G). <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/6599>
- Rosas, N. K. (2022). An exploration of teacher self-efficacy in itinerant teachers (Doctoral dissertation, Concordia University Texas). <https://www.proquest.com/openview/ae59ca823be7b92a9c92a116810a5583/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
- Rossini, V. (2021). «Follow a rule of life». Classroom management and positive discipline in an Apulian Children's House. *Ricerche di Pedagogia e Didattica*. *Journal of Theories and Research in Education*, 16(2), 117-132 <https://doi.org/10.6092/issn.1970-2221/12187>
- Sandwick, T., Hahn, J. W., & Hassoun Ayoub, L. (2019). Fostering community, sharing power: Lessons for building restorative justice school cultures. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 27(145), n145. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1235090>
- Santa Cruz, F. F., & D'Angelo, G. (2020). Positive discipline for the development of emotional abilities. *Revista de Investigacion Psicologica*, (24), 53-74. http://www.scielo.org.bo/scielo.php?pid=S222330322020000200005&script=sci_abstract&tlng=en
- Schutt, R. K. (2018). *Investigating the social world: The process and practice of research*. Sage publications. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1319118>
- Sege, R. D., Siegel, B. S., ABUSE, C. O. C., Flaherty, E. G., Gavril, A. R., Idzerda, S. M., ... & committee on psychological aspects of child and family health. (2018). Effective discipline to raise healthy children. *Pediatrics*, 142(6). <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2018-3112>
- Slee, R. (2020). *Changing theories and practices of discipline*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315865522>
- Smith, J. E., & Meyers, R. J. (2022). *The CRAFT treatment manual for substance use problems: Working with family members*. Guilford Publications. <https://www.guilford.com/books/The-CRAFT-Treatment-Manual-for-Substance-Use-Problems/Smith-Meyers/9781462551101>
- Sprague, J. R., & Walker, H. M. (2021). *Safe and healthy schools: Practical prevention strategies*. Guilford Publications.

<https://www.guilford.com/books/Safe-and-Healthy-Schools/Sprague-Walker/9781462547814>

Sprick, J., Sprick, R., Edwards, J., & Coughlin, C. (2021). CHAMPS: A proactive & positive approach to classroom management. Safe & civil schools. Ancora Publishing. 21 West 6th Avenue, Eugene, OR 97401. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED615489>

Stevens, A. (2018). Positive discipline as a part of effective classroom management. https://scholarworks.wmich.edu/honors_theses/2973/

Sudirman, A., Lie, D., Sherly, S., & Dharma, E. (2019). The impact of work discipline and work ethic on the teacher performance of Sultan Agung Pematangsiantar private middle school teachers TA 2018/2019. *International Journal of Business Studies*, 3(3), 125-135. <https://doi.org/10.32924/ijbs.v3i3.83>

Sugai, G., & Horner, R. H. (2020). Sustaining and scaling positive behavioral interventions and supports: Implementation drivers, outcomes, and considerations. *Exceptional children*, 86(2), 120-136. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0014402919855331>

Swain-Bradway, J., Gulbrandson, K., Galston, A., & McIntosh, K. (2019). Do Wisconsin schools implementing an integrated academic and behavior support framework improve equity in academic and school discipline outcomes?. Technical Assistance Center on Positive Behavioral Interventions and Supports. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED594998>

Tartari, E. (2018). The impact of positive discipline in the learning process. In ICERI2018 Proceedings (pp. 8245-8249). IATED. <https://doi.org/10.21125/iceri.2018.0496>

Taylor, E., & Kearney, A. (2018). School discipline and surveillance: Developments in Australia and Aotearoa/New Zealand. The Palgrave International Handbook of School Discipline, Surveillance, and Social Control, 87-104. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-71559-9_5

Termes, A., Edwards Jr, D. B., & Verger, A. (2020). The development and dynamics of public-private partnerships in the Philippines' education: A counterintuitive case of school choice, competition, and privatization. *Educational Policy*, 34(1), 91-117. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904819886323>

Trigueros, R., Padilla, A., Aguilar-Parra, J. M., Mercader, I., López-Liria, R., & Rocamora, P. (2020). The influence of transformational teacher leadership on academic motivation and resilience, burnout and academic performance. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(20), 7687. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17207687>

Trinidad, J. E. (2022). Rationalising punishment: A cyberethnography of Filipino teachers' resistance to positive discipline <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/agdu2>

Tyre, A., Feuerborn, L., Beaudoin, K., & Bruce, J. (2020). Middle school teachers' concerns for implementing the principles of SWPBIS. *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions*, 22(2), 93-104. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098300719867858>

Valente, S., Monteiro, A. P., & Lourenço, A. A. (2019). The relationship between teachers' emotional intelligence and classroom discipline management. *Psychology in the Schools*, 56(5), 741-750. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.22218>

Van den Berg, P. (2020). The development of a work integrated learning mentoring framework for a faculty of education (Doctoral dissertation, North-West University (South Africa)). <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1603-0365>

Van Laar, E., Van Deursen, A. J., Van Dijk, J. A., & De Haan, J. (2020). Determinants of 21st-century skills and 21st-century digital skills for workers: A systematic literature review. *Sage Open*, 10(1), 2158244019900176. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019900176>

Walker, B. L. T. (2020). "Loud, proud, and love a crowd:" African American girls and school discipline practices. *Middle School Journal*, 51(1), 12-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00940771.2019.1689776>

Wang, M. T., Degol, J. L., Amemiya, J., Parr, A., & Guo, J. (2020). Classroom climate and children's academic and psychological wellbeing: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Developmental Review*, 57, 100912. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dr.2020.100912>

Wang, W. L., & Kuo, C. Y. (2019). Relationships among teachers' positive discipline, students' well-being and teachers' effective teaching: A study of special education teachers and adolescent students with learning disabilities in Taiwan. *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 66(1), 82-98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1034912X.2018.1441978>

Warnick, B. R., & Scribner, C. F. (2020). Discipline, punishment, and the moral community of schools. *Theory and Research in Education*, 18(1), 98-116. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1477878520904943>

Webster-Stratton, C., & Reid, M. J. (2018). The incredible years parents, teachers, and children training series: A multifaceted treatment approach for young children with conduct problems. <https://doi.org/10.1037/11488-003>

Wei, L. F., Chang, S. H., & Lin, C. Y. (2018). A study on the effect of students' perception of teachers' positive discipline on bullying prevention in primary schools in the Taiwan region. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 8(5). <https://www.ijiet.org/vol8/1065-ER1015.pdf>

- Welsh, R. O., & Little, S. (2018). The school discipline dilemma: A comprehensive review of disparities and alternative approaches. *Review of Educational Research*, 88(5), 752-794. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654318791582>
- Welsh, R. O., Rodriguez, L. A., & Joseph, B. B. (2023). Beating the school discipline odds: conceptualizing and examining inclusive disciplinary schools in New York City. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2023.2182795>
- Whitney, T., & Ackerman, K. B. (2020). Acknowledging student behavior: A review of methods promoting positive and constructive feedback. *Beyond Behavior*, 29(2), 86-94. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1074295620902474>
- Williams, R. (2020). *Culture and materialism*. Verso Books. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1367549417732998>
- with positive behavioral interventions and supports: The case of one disadvantaged urban South African Primary School. *South African Journal of Childhood Education*, 11(1), 1-9: <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajce.v11i1.1022>
- World Health Organization. (2019). *School-based violence prevention: A practical handbook*. Williams, K. E., Berthelsen, D., & Walker, S. (2020). Evaluation of a drama-based social and emotional learning program on the self-esteem and well-being of primary school students. *School Mental Health*, 12(1), 112-124. <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/324930/9789241515542-eng.pdf>
- Zhou, Y., Liu, H., & Yang, X. (2019). The influence of mentorship on novice teachers' professional development in positive discipline. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 86, 102910. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2024.104519>
- Zhu, Q., Cheong, Y., Wang, C., & Sun, C. (2022). The roles of resilience, peer relationship, teacher–student relationship on student mental health difficulties during COVID-19. *School Psychology*, 37(1), 62. <https://doi.org/10.1037/spq0000492>

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